

Investigation of the low-lying nuclear
structure of ^{192}Hg through γ -ray decay
spectroscopy

C. Paxman

A dissertation submitted to the Department of Physics,
University of Surrey, in partial fulfilment of the degree of
Master in Physics

January 2020

Abstract

Neutron-deficient nuclei in the region of the magic number $Z = 82$ are known to exhibit strong shape deformation and shape coexistence. Fingerprints of these phenomena can be seen in the energy level structure of the nucleus, which has driven efforts to build a solid base of experimental knowledge in this region of isotopes. One such isotope, ^{192}Hg , lies on the boundary of the shape coexisting region, but has not been investigated for almost 40 years. This investigation is an analysis of electron capture decay data taken at TRIUMF-ISAC in 2017. This experiment uses the powerful γ -ray spectroscopy of GRIFFIN to expand our experimental knowledge of ^{192}Hg , applying γ - γ angular correlation techniques for the first time. Present literature identifies 74 γ -rays in this decay – this work expands that number to 240, from which an additional 28 transitions have been found. Additionally, five γ - γ angular correlations results are presented, from which the mixing ratios of decays can be obtained.

Declaration of originality

This dissertation and the work to which it refers are the results of my own efforts. Any ideas, data, images or text resulting from the work of others (whether published or unpublished) are fully identified as such within the work and attributed to their originator in the text, bibliography or in footnotes. This dissertation has not been submitted in whole or in part for any other academic degree or professional qualification. I agree that the University has the right to submit my work to the plagiarism detection service TurnitinUK for originality checks.

Acknowledgement

My time at TRIUMF has been the greatest learning experience of my life, and I am unbelievably lucky for being afforded this opportunity. I would like to acknowledge my supervisors Prof. Paddy Regan and Dr. Adam Garnsworthy for their guidance and professional support through this year – their advice has provided me with a clear image of what I want my career to become, and for that I am incredibly grateful.

I am indebted to Bruno and Stephen for fielding my incessant questions, and spending far more of their precious time helping than they probably should have. Their guidance has been invaluable - thank you.

I would also like to thank my friends and colleagues for their kindness and throughout this year. Chris, Carlotta and Daniel have welcomed me with unprecedented warmth, and truly made Vancouver a home. I could never thank them enough for the wonderful times we had together, and I can only hope we will cross paths again.

Last, but far from least, I would like to wholeheartedly thank Ellie, for always being there for me, no matter how stressed I became. These last few weeks have been the most intense in my educational career by far, and I would not have made it through at all without her. Thank you, beautiful.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Précis of Literature Review	1
1.1.1	Nuclear shapes & coexistence	1
1.1.2	Structural features of shape coexistence	3
1.1.3	Interest in ^{192}Hg	5
1.1.4	Theoretical background	6
1.1.5	Previous works	7
1.2	Angular distribution of gamma rays	9
1.3	^{192}Tl electron capture decay	11
1.4	Summary	13
2	Experimental techniques	16
2.1	TRIUMF	16
2.1.1	Cyclotron	17
2.1.2	ISAC	18
2.2	GRIFFIN	22
2.2.1	Tape system	24
2.2.2	HPGe Array	26
2.2.3	Ancillary detectors	27
2.2.3.1	‘Outer’ detectors	28
2.2.3.2	‘Inner’ detectors	28
2.2.4	Data Acquisition System	29
2.3	S1607 Experiment	30
2.3.1	Beam yield and composition	30
2.3.2	Tape cycling	30
2.3.3	Detector arrangement	33
2.3.4	DAQ issues	34

3	Analytical techniques	35
3.1	Calibration	35
3.2	Simple γ spectroscopy	41
3.3	γ - γ Coincidence	43
3.3.1	Creation of γ - γ coincidence spectra	44
3.3.1.1	Time-random background subtraction	44
3.3.1.2	Compton scattering	48
3.3.1.3	Coincidence gating	48
3.3.2	Analysis of γ - γ coincidence spectra	50
3.3.2.1	Peak fitting procedure	50
3.3.2.2	Treatment of doublets	51
3.4	γ - γ Angular Correlation	54
3.4.1	Analysis of experimental data	54
3.4.1.1	Physical geometry of GRIFFIN	54
3.4.1.2	Theory of the event mixing technique	55
3.4.1.3	Event mixing in practice	57
3.4.2	Comparison to theory and extraction of results	59
3.4.2.1	Parameterization of angular correlation	59
3.4.2.2	Detector arrangement corrections	60
4	Results and discussion	63
4.1	γ -rays and γ -ray coincidences	63
4.2	γ - γ angular correlation results	64
4.2.1	422.7 keV and 634.7 keV	64
4.2.2	745.4 keV and 173.9 keV	68
4.2.3	634.7 keV and 786.3 keV	70
4.2.4	786.3 keV and 343.0 keV	72
4.2.5	422.7 keV and 1112.6 keV	75
4.3	Proposed updated level scheme	77
4.3.1	Placing of doublet peaks	77
4.3.1.1	1112.6 keV and 1113.8 keV	77
4.3.1.2	690.7 keV, 692.6 keV and 694.3 keV	79
4.3.1.3	731.9 keV and 733.5 keV	80
4.3.1.4	675.3 keV and 676.3 keV	80
4.3.1.5	714.0 keV, 716.4 keV, 718.1 keV and 720.5 keV	81
4.3.1.6	477.3 keV and 480.3 keV	83
4.3.1.7	383.9 keV and 384.8 keV	83
4.3.1.8	557.5 keV and 559.5 keV	84

4.3.1.9	1418.8 keV and 1422.7 keV	84
4.3.2	Spin assignments	85
4.3.3	Table of levels and transitions	87
5	Conclusions	90
5.1	Results of this investigation	90
5.2	Future work	92
A	Literature Review and Interim Report	103
B	Using χ^2 analysis techniques	132
C	Table of observed γ-rays	135

List of Figures

1.1	Geometric models of nuclear shape deformations.	2
1.2	Energy level scheme of $^{172-206}\text{Hg}$, showing the normal and intruder levels	4
1.3	Comparison of three theoretical angular distributions from different cascades	11
1.4	Mass parabola diagram for nuclei with $A = 192$	14
2.1	Diagram of the <i>Isotope Separator and Accelerator</i> (ISAC) facility	19
2.2	Picture of the GRIFFIN spectrometer	21
2.3	GRIFFIN's rhombicuboctahedral geometry	22
2.4	Top-down schematic of GRIFFIN, with directions marked . . .	23
2.5	Two examples of growth-decay cycles over the length of a tape cycle. These are for decays of (a) ^{160}Eu and (b) ^{128}Cd . Note the vastly different timescales due to the different half-lives - 380s of implantation in (a), compared to 10s in (b).	25
2.6	Diagram of a GRIFFIN HPGe clover	27
2.7	Decay chain of ^{192}Tl to stable ^{192}Pt	32
3.1	Comparison of the Akima and polynomial fitting procedures .	36
3.4	Efficiency curve of the GRIFFIN spectrometer	42
3.5	A partial level scheme of ^{192}Hg , demonstrating γ - γ coincidence analysis	44
3.6	A histogram of time interval between γ -rays, demonstrating time-random background	45
3.7	Time-random background corrected 2D histogram, for the region $E_{\gamma,1}, E_{\gamma,2} < 1500$ keV	47
3.8	User interface of the TBGSubtraction tool	49
3.9	Comparison of three partial spectra of the 1100 keV to 1125 keV region, revealing the 1112.6 keV - 1113.8 keV doublet	52

3.10	Example of fitting multiple RADWARE peaks	53
3.11	Examples of the stages of the event mixing technique.	56
4.1	422.7 keV-634.7 keV: γ - γ angular correlation diagram	65
4.2	422.7 keV-634.7 keV: χ^2 /NDF comparison of potential spin assignments.	66
4.3	745.4 keV-173.9 keV: γ - γ angular correlation diagram	68
4.4	745.4 keV-173.9 keV: χ^2 /NDF comparison of potential spin assignments.	69
4.5	634.7 keV-786.3 keV: γ - γ angular correlation diagram	70
4.6	634.7 keV-786.3 keV: χ^2 /NDF comparison of potential spin assignments.	71
4.7	786.3 keV-343.0 keV: γ - γ angular correlation diagram	72
4.8	786.3 keV-343.0 keV: χ^2 /NDF comparison of potential spin assignments.	73
4.9	422.7 keV-1112.6 keV: γ - γ angular correlation diagram	75
4.10	422.7 keV-1112.6 keV: χ^2 /NDF comparison of potential spin assignments.	76
4.11	Proposed level scheme for ^{192}Hg	78

List of Tables

2.1	Positions of HPGe detectors in GRIFFIN during this experiment	33
3.1	All calibration sources and peaks used during this experiment	40
3.2	Results of A.D. MacLean's investigation of the effects of non-standard detector distances	62
4.1	Table of the levels and transitions in ^{192}Hg	87
C.1	Table of observed γ -rays	135

Chapter 1

Introduction

A document providing a detailed background and introduction for this dissertation was submitted in July 2019, for partial fulfillment of unit PHY3058. A brief summary is provided here. For a more detailed discussion of the topics presented here, please see *Appendix A*.

1.1 Précis of Literature Review

1.1.1 Nuclear shapes & coexistence

Over the last half-century, our understanding of the nucleus has evolved greatly. While we used to believe that nuclei were spherical objects - or at least, spherical distributions of protons and neutrons - we now know that they can be far more complex than that. There are actually various eigenstates (static forms) of nuclei where nucleon-nucleon interactions distort the overall

Figure 1.1: Geometric representations of the most commonly observed nuclear shapes, where colour represents the deviation from the spherical radius (blue is negative, red is positive). From left to right: spherical, prolate spheroid and oblate spheroid. Prolate and oblate deformations are quadrupole in nature. Partial figure from Ref. [1].

distribution of particles, making the nucleus non-spherical. This is not at all uncommon, and occurs frequently throughout the nuclear chart.

These deformed shapes can be quite complex, but the most common are the two quadrupole deformations – prolate (like a rugby ball) and oblate (like a curling stone) – shown in Fig 1.1. The deformation is driven by the tensor component of the monopole interaction of protons and neutrons, described in great depth by T. Otsuka (2016) [2].

Nuclear shapes are interesting in and of themselves, as they give some insight into the complex and often mysterious forces that are at play in large nuclei. This became even more fascinating when, in the mid 20th Century, it was first observed that a nucleus could exhibit distinct nuclear shapes – and hence, different *behaviours* – at very similar energy levels. When levels occur at close energies like this, quantum state mixing can occur [3]. This phenomenon, known as *shape coexistence*, quickly became an important avenue of study in the field of nuclear structure. This structure was largely

inexplicable using the nuclear theories of the time, and seemed to point to interesting behaviours that we are still studying today. Heyde and Wood's 2011 evaluation of the field of shape coexistence [4] discusses the possibility that this phenomenon may be responsible for the collapse of the nuclear shell structure, placing great importance in these studies. Shape coexistence has even been linked to the suppression of fission decay and, therefore, the superheavy island of stability [2]. As such, shape coexistence is one of the great challenges of modern nuclear structure physics.

1.1.2 Structural features of shape coexistence

While only some very specific and complex experiments can truly measure the shape of a nucleus (see *Appendix A, Section III.B.3*), there is a simple feature of the energy level structure that can be a very useful fingerprint. Intruding deformed states will approach lower energies gradually across isotopic (constant Z) and isotonic (constant N) chains – in some cases, dropping low enough to become the ground state* – with maximal coexistence occurring near the midshell [4]. As such, the emergence of shape coexistence can often be indicated by a second rotational band at unusually low energies. For these purposes, a rotational band in an even-even nucleus is characterized by levels with $J = (0, 2, 4, \dots)$.

Such an intrusion can be seen in Fig. 1.2. In this figure, there is a set

*Note that the 'ground state' is the lowest energy state, which is arbitrarily assigned an excitation energy of 0 keV

Figure 1.2: An energy level scheme for even Z , even N isotopes in the range $^{172-206}\text{Hg}$. Blue squares indicate normal configuration states, with spherical or weakly deformed shape. Red circles indicate the intruder configuration, with more deformed shape (which is oblate, in this case [5]). Figure from Ref. [6].

of levels that have reasonably constant excitation energy across the whole chain, shown in blue squares. This is the ground state band (built upon the 0_1^+ ground state level), and in almost all cases, also the yrast states[†]. There is also a second set of levels, shown in red circles, that follow a parabolic curve across isotopes with a minimum near the midshell ($t^{182}\text{Hg}$) – these are the aforementioned intruding states. This band of levels is built upon the first excited 0^+ state (0_2^+), which makes the identification of the 0_2^+ state vital for

[†]‘Yrast states’ are the lowest-energy state with a given spin assignment, such as the first 2^+ state, 2_1^+ .

the systematic study of shape coexistence and its emergence.

Shape coexistence is found to occur across the nuclear chart, in all but the lightest nuclei, but the neutron deficient nuclei in the region of the magic number $Z = 82$ has been especially enlightening to study. This region exhibits “the most extensive manifestation of shape coexistence known anywhere on the nuclear mass surface” [4]. Mercury (Hg), with an atomic number of $Z = 80$, falls in this region of interest.

1.1.3 Interest in ^{192}Hg

The current literature regarding the low-lying, low-spin energy levels of ^{192}Hg is almost 40 years old, and – while informative when it was published – fails to establish many points of interest, such as providing confident spin-parity assignments outside of the ground state band, or locating the 0_2^+ state. These have been found for all of the neighbouring isotopes – ^{192}Hg is the weak link in this isotopic chain.

This neglect of ^{192}Hg is likely due to its position on the borderline of the often-studied intruder region and the easily-studied stable region. Studying the transition between these two regions of the isotopic chain could reveal interesting physics, as this presents an opportunity to study the ‘normal’ configuration of nucleons in neutron deficient Hg, without the added complications of the low-lying intruder configuration and the resulting interband transitions. It could also be argued that having a fuller understanding of the isotopes in this transitory stage can provide greater constraints on theoretical

models of shape coexistence.

1.1.4 Theoretical background

Theoretical and experimental physics are symbiotic and largely inextricable. As such, systematic analyses of isotopic and isotonic chains are important in order to more accurately inform theoretical explanations. The marked lack of experimental data regarding ^{192}Hg has meant that the theoretical models of this nucleus – and the isotopic chain – have suffered.

There are, at present, two theoretical studies that have tackled ^{192}Hg – the 2013 study by Nomura *et al.* [7], and the 2014 study by García-Ramos & Heyde [8]. They both use the *Interacting Boson Model* (IBM) of the nucleus, which incorporates aspects of the shell model, with refinement from collective models to account for interactions such as the nucleon pairing effect. For even-even isotopes, the IBM simplifies a nucleus into an inert core, and any remaining nucleons are put into identical pairs, represented as bosons. See Ref. [9] for more details.

García-Ramos & Heyde use a version of the IBM that treats nucleons as indistinguishable particles, but allows for mixing between the states – the *Interacting Boson Model with Configuration Mixing* (IBM-CM). This method replicates observation accurately, but it is not an independent theoretical model. It is based on the χ^2 minimization[‡] of parameters compared to experimental results, such as the energy or strength of a transition. This makes

[‡]The reader is referred to Appendix B for an overview of χ^2 minimization

the model very dependant on the accuracy and reliability of the experimental data, and causes notable weakness in areas where no data is available. Despite this, the observed trends and shape structures are well reproduced, and the calculated values for lifetimes and reduced transition probabilities in the $^{172-200}\text{Hg}$ region closely predict recent measurements [10].

Nomura *et al.* use a different version of the IBM which does not allow for mixing between configurations and treats protons and neutrons as unique particles. This method, IBM-2, is a pure theoretical method, independent of experimental values. Nomura *et al.*'s IBM-2 calculations are often less accurate than García-Ramos & Heyde's IBM-CM counterpart, as they suffered from a simplistic mathematical model and a high sensitivity to the energy density function chosen to restrain the variables [11]. The trends of low-lying yrast states are well reproduced, but high-spin or non-yrast states are less accurate, and do not follow the experimental trends.

Overall, IBM-CM has a much greater predictive power than IBM-2, and can be more reliably used to direct experimental studies. In turn, establishing a firmer experimental understanding of the low-lying structure would be able to facilitate more accurate IBM-CM studies in the future, highlighting the importance of such work.

1.1.5 Previous works

The present knowledge of low-lying, low-spin energy levels of ^{192}Hg is based on three studies, published between 1968 and 1981. These studies were

instrumental in establishing an early level scheme, but the efficiencies and resolutions of the detectors placed a limit on what could be observed.

Petry *et al.* [12] was the first study to establish the energies and coincidences of the most intense γ -rays in the decay of this isotope. The energy level diagram proposed was corroborated by future studies, but there were only 7 levels and 8 transitions presented.

Vandlik *et al.* [13] expanded that level scheme and identified 40 previously unobserved γ -rays, but their study only used one Ge(Li) γ -ray detector, so they were unable to identify γ - γ coincidences (see Chapter 3.3). This means that they built their level scheme through comparison to neighbouring isotopes. This is a somewhat weak way to construct a level scheme, susceptible to inaccuracies due to unpredicted changes in nuclear structure, or false placements propagating from neighbour to neighbour.

Sousa *et al.* [14] expanded the number of known γ -rays to 74, and assigned 31 of these to transitions in a 22-state level scheme. Though contradicting Vandlik *et al.* in places, evidence supporting Sousa *et al.*'s level scheme was far more comprehensive and compelling, which inspires confidence in the validity of their level scheme. As a result, the current *Evaluated Nuclear Structure Data File* (ENSDF) sheet for ^{192}Hg (through electron capture decay of ^{192}Tl) is based almost solely on Sousa *et al.*'s findings.

1.2 Angular distribution of gamma rays

While some techniques such as collinear laser spectroscopy [15] can firmly assign spins to the ground state of nucleus, it is more difficult to firmly assign the spins of excited states. Often, this is done by finding the multipolarity[§] of transitions between the unknown state and a known state (such as the ground state). Analysis of the angle between emitted γ -rays can determine these multipolarities using a physical feature of nuclear transitions; the angular distribution of γ -rays.

Take, for example, two successive transitions – γ_1 and γ_2 – in *randomly oriented* nuclei. When taken individually, there is no preference for the direction that a γ -ray will be emitted in. This is because even if there is an anisotropic emission of γ -rays from one nucleus, the random orientation of many nuclei ensures that the overall observed radiation is isotropic. However, the angle between γ_1 and γ_2 emitted from the same nucleus can be found independently of the nuclear orientation. The probability distribution of this relative angle is determined by the multipolarity of the γ -rays [16] [17].

In the case of randomly oriented nuclei with short-lived intermediate nuclear states, the probability that γ_1 and γ_2 are emitted with an angle of θ

[§]The multipolarity of a transition is the amount of angular momentum carried away by the emitted photon. Transitions can be of electric or magnetic character, though this does not influence the angular distribution of γ -rays.

between them (W) is proportional to

$$W(\theta) = \sum_{i=0,\text{even}}^{\infty} A_{ii} P_i(\cos \theta)$$

where $P_i(\cos \theta)$ are Legendre polynomials and A_{ii} is a series of coefficients related to transition multipolarity and nuclear state parity [18]. Smith et al. (2019) [18] propose the use of a truncated version of this equation for β -decay experiments such as this one, as these tend to involve low-spin nuclear states, meaning that high-order coefficients of the sum become negligible. They instead rewrite the equation as

$$W(\theta) = A_{00} [1 + a_2 P_2(\cos \theta) + a_4 P_4(\cos \theta)]$$

where $a_2 = A_{22}/A_{00}$ and $a_4 = A_{44}/A_{00}$.

As the Legendre polynomials are well-known, the angular distribution probability $W(\theta)$ is now defined by the coefficients A_{00} , a_2 and a_4 . These coefficients can be found experimentally by comparing the number of counts detected at an angle θ against different theoretical functions $W(\theta)$. The method to produce experimental graphs of detected counts against $\cos \theta$ will be discussed in Chapter 3.4, but examples of the theoretical curves for the transitions $J_i \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 0$ (where $J_i = 0, 2, 4$)[¶] can be seen in Fig. 1.3. Note that the $0 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 0$ angular distribution is especially unique compared to other cascades, which is important as it would allow the experimenter to

[¶]Parity is not given, as this technique is not sensitive to the parity of states.

Figure 1.3: A comparison of three theoretical angular distributions from different cascades; a $0 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 0$ (green dot-dash line), a $2 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 0$ (dashed red line) and a $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 0$ (solid blue line).

easily identify such a transition, even with poor statistics or few data points.

This type of spectroscopy is γ - γ *angular correlation* analysis.

1.3 ^{192}Tl electron capture decay

This document focuses on the *electron capture decay* of ^{192}Tl to ^{192}Hg – this section aims to provide pertinent context for these terms.

The most basic view of nuclear β decay is that decays where Z increases are β^- (electron emission) and those where Z decreases are β^+ (positron

emission), but this is often not the case. Electron capture (ϵ) is a form of nuclear beta decay which competes with β^+ decay. They both reduce the number of protons and increase the number of neutrons in the system, but while β^+ decay requires the creation of a positron and an electron neutrino, electron capture instead absorbs an existing electron from the atomic shells, i.e. [19]

In order for a decay to occur, the Q -value of the decay (energy released) must be positive. β^+ decay requires the mass-energy difference of ${}^A_Z X_N$ and ${}^A_{Z-1} X'_{N+1}$ to be large enough to create two leptons (when using atomic masses), which means that energetic barrier for β^+ decay is $2m_e c^2$ larger than for electron capture, so in most cases electron capture is preferred. This is given in [19] as

$$\begin{aligned}Q_{\beta^+} &= [m({}^A X) - m({}^A X') - 2m_e] c^2 \\ Q_{\epsilon} &= [m({}^A X) - m({}^A X')] c^2 \\ Q_{\beta^+} &= Q_{\epsilon} - 2m_e c^2\end{aligned}$$

As the Q -value of a decay is so heavily influenced by the mass disparity between ${}^A X$ and ${}^A X'$, the instability of a nucleus is dependant largely on the mass excess of the nucleus - that is, the difference between the mass of the

actual nucleus and its mass number (A). The lighter the nucleus with respect to mass number, then the greater the binding energy and the more stable the system. For isobars (nuclei with the same mass number, but different atomic numbers) this stability is often represented in mass parabola diagrams. The mass parabola for $A = 192$ is shown in Fig. 1.4. There are two parabolic lines, one for odd- Z nuclei and one for even- Z nuclei, as unpaired nucleons decrease the binding energy of the system. The β decays of the nuclei are shown by the red and blue dotted lines, which cascade from high to low masses, until they reach one of the local minima. From this graph, it can be seen that the two points with the lowest total mass are ^{192}Os ($Z = 76$) and ^{192}Pt ($Z = 78$), which are both stable nuclei.^{||}

When starting from pure ^{192}Tl , it is clear from the mass parabola (and confirmed by literature [20]) that ^{192}Tl decays to ^{192}Hg , ^{192}Au and ^{192}Pt , where it reaches stability. Each of these decays are electron capture decays. This short decay path becomes relevant in Chapter 2.3.2.

1.4 Summary

Detailed experimental observation of nuclear structure through γ -ray spectroscopy is a reliable and comparatively simple method of identifying areas of interest where shape coexistence may occur. This can help to focus the

^{||}Even though ^{192}Pt is the *global* minimum, there is no viable β decay from ^{192}Os , as β decay can only change Z by ± 1 and both of those changes would *increase* the mass of the system. Therefore, ^{192}Os is β stable.

Figure 1.4: Mass parabola diagram for nuclei with $A = 192$, plotting atomic mass in atomic mass units, u, against atomic number, Z. There are two solid black parabolas, for odd and even nuclei. Possible β decay paths are marked with dashed lines. Blue dashed lines are β^- decay paths, red dashed lines are ϵ decay paths

attention of other experiments which can directly determine nuclear shape. Expanding and improving our experimental knowledge in this way is key to improving theoretical models, which can in turn lead to a better understanding of the nucleus and its many complex interactions.

The isotope ^{192}Hg is in the unique position of being located at the transition between the shape coexisting midshell region, and the non-shape coexisting stable region. By improving our understanding of this transition, we can more confidently delineate the region where intruding states are signif-

icant, and therefore provide better constraints for future theoretical studies of the neutron-deficient Hg isotopes. There have been no γ -ray spectroscopy studies of this isotope in nearly four decades, and much of the low-lying structure is uncertain or unknown.

Future experiments, and theoretical model calculations, would benefit greatly from a more comprehensive understanding of the low-lying states of Hg. To facilitate this, an *angular correlation* technique can be used to confidently identify the spin state of nuclear levels.

The decay path of ^{192}Tl is well understood. Mass-energy arguments ensure that ^{192}Tl decays by electron capture three times into stable ^{192}Pt . The implications of this decay path this analysis will be discussed in Chapter 2.3.2.

Chapter 2

Experimental techniques

In 2017, γ -ray spectroscopy of ^{192}Hg was performed using the GRIFFIN facility in ISAC, TRIUMF. This chapter will introduce these facilities, starting with the widest view and narrowing in scope through the chapter.

2.1 TRIUMF

TRIUMF is Canada's national particle accelerator centre, founded in 1968 in Vancouver, British Columbia [21]. TRIUMF operations are primarily focused on experimental nuclear physics research, but have expanded through the years to include experimental and theoretical groups working in particle physics, materials science and nuclear medicine.

2.1.1 Cyclotron

There are various experimental facilities on the 13 acre TRIUMF site, most of which rely upon the proton beam delivered by the 520 MeV cyclotron at the heart of the facility.

An initial ion source provides a beam of H^- ions (one proton, with two orbiting electrons) to the TRIUMF cyclotron. The cyclotron accelerates the injected beam from its initial energy of 300 keV to a maximum energy of 520 MeV. Operating energies for the various experimental facilities can vary between 83 MeV and 500 MeV [22], and proton beam can be delivered simultaneously to different areas of TRIUMF. Six magnets apply a magnetic field to the ions, which induces circular motion in the ion beam, spiralling outwards as it accelerates. The ions are then incident upon a graphite stripping foil, which removes the two orbital electrons from the beam particle [23]. This results in a beam of protons, which are deflected the opposite way by the magnetic field and channeled out of the cyclotron through various beamlines, eventually being transported to the experimental halls.

The ISAC facility, which is where this experiment was conducted, is supplied by beamline 2A, with a typical operating energy of 500 MeV and a typical current of $70 \mu\text{A}$. [22]

2.1.2 ISAC

The *Isotope Separator and Accelerator* (ISAC) facility is a key member of TRIUMF's experimental operations. It is an Isotope Separation On-line (ISOL) facility which receives the proton beam from the cyclotron, and outputs a high-purity *radioactive ion beam* (RIB) to two experimental halls, ISAC-I and ISAC-II. The ISAC-I hall is the low-medium energy section, which houses many detector systems, including GRIFFIN. The facility, shown in Fig. 2.1, can currently produce a viable experimental yield of 69 different elements. There are several complex stages to this process, which are summarised here.

Target chamber. The proton beam is received into one of two target stations, where it impinges upon a series of thin foils – for example, uranium carbide foils (UC_x). Carbide composite target foils are preferred for their ability to withstand high temperatures, allowing for high operating currents and more intense experimental beams [24]. The proton beam induces fragmentation (splitting into multiple lighter nuclei) and spallation (ejection of nucleons) of the uranium nuclei. The target chamber now contains diverse nuclei - in theory, any element lighter than uranium can be produced. These isotopes have high kinetic energy, so elements with low ionization energies can *surface ionize* on the walls of the chamber.

There is a second chamber perpendicular to the direction of the proton beam (see Fig. 2.1). This ion acceleration chamber has a 20 kV potential difference applied across its length, as opposed to the electrically neutral

Figure 2.1: Diagram of the ISAC beam production facility, showing the two target stations, *TRIUMF Resonant Ionization Laser Ion Source* (TRILIS) laser and mass separator. Figure taken from Ref. [24]

target chamber. Ionized and non-ionized nuclei from the target chamber can thermally diffuse into this chamber. Ions in the acceleration chamber experience a force due to the large potential difference, which accelerates the ion to approximately 20 keV. This method can be used to provide RIB for experiments.

TRILIS. Surface ionization favours elements with low ionization energies, such as alkali metals, so RIB of elements with higher ionization energies will

have significantly lower yield. One method to produce high yield, high purity beams is to selectively ionise the elements in the target chamber.

The *TRIUMF Resonant Ionization Laser Ion Source* (TRILIS) is an arrangement of several lasers; a *neodymium-doped yttrium aluminium garnet* (Nd:YAG) laser simultaneously pumps three *titanium-sapphire* (Ti:Sa) lasers [25][26]. The Ti:Sa lasers are tuned to the resonant frequencies of electron excitation energies. Preferably, these three excitations should be able to reach a self-ionizing state. As the electron structure of each element is unique, elements can be selectively ionized with the tuned lasers. Using TRILIS will greatly increase the yield of the RIB element, but it cannot prevent surface ionized contaminants from entering the beam [27]. Additionally, TRILIS can select by element, but cannot distinguish isotopes of the same element as effectively. For this, a mass separator is used.

Mass separator. The mass and charge of an isotope beam determines its magnetic rigidity, $B\rho$, which is defined as;

$$B\rho = \frac{kp}{Q}$$

where p is the momentum of the beam particle, Q is the charge of the beam particle, and k is a constant. The magnetic rigidity relates the properties of the nucleus to the force it would experience in a magnetic field - lighter or more charged (low p or high Q) nuclei are deflected more than heavier or less charged (high p or low Q) nuclei. By passing the 20 keV accelerated beam

Figure 2.2: Picture of the eastern hemisphere of the GRIFFIN spectrometer. Beam direction marked with a red arrow (left). Point of beam implantation and nuclear decay marked with yellow star. The arrangement shown includes; 1) *High Purity Germanium* (HPGe) detectors (obscured by suppressors), 2) $\text{LaBr}_3(\text{Ce})$ detectors, 3) *Deuterated Scintillator Array for Neutron Tagging* (DESCANT), 4) *Scintillating Electron-Positron Tagging Array* (SCEPTAR) upstream, 5) SCEPTAR downstream, 6) Mylar tape collection system.

from the target chamber through a tuned magnetic field, the contaminating isotopes with different $B\rho$ values (for example, the surface-ionizing alkaline metals) can be filtered out of the beam. The ISAC mass separator has a mass resolution of $1/5000$ [24].

2.2 GRIFFIN

The *Gamma-Ray Infrastructure For Fundamental Investigations of Nuclei* (GRIFFIN) array is a system of up to 16 HPGe γ -ray detectors situated at ISAC-I, designed for decay spectroscopy of stopped beams. Commissioned in 2014 and jointly funded by TRIUMF and the University of Guelph, GRIFFIN has applications in the research of nuclear structure, astrophysical processes and fundamental symmetries. [28]

Each of the 16 detector units contains four HPGe crystals in a clover formation, for a total of 64 distinct detection channels (see Chapter 2.2.2). These 16 detectors are arranged in such a way as to make up the square surfaces of a rhombicuboctahedron, shown in Fig. 2.3. GRIFFIN is versatile by design, and is compatible with a swathe of ancillary detectors to allow users the option to collect a range of additional data alongside γ spectra.

The detector systems fall into two categories; the *outer* detectors that are mounted on GRIFFIN's structural skeleton, and the *inner* detectors within the target chamber, which are under vacuum during operation.

Figure 2.3: Geometry of GRIFFIN's HPGe faces when packed closely in the array. This is a rhombicuboctahedron, with each square face divided into four, for each crystal in the detector. Ancillary detectors can be placed in the triangular face. Partial figure from Ref. [18].

Figure 2.4: A top-down schematic of the GRIFFIN array. The western hemisphere is shown in orange, and the eastern hemisphere in blue. Thick lines delineate the corona and the lampshades. The upstream component of the inner detector array is shown in green, the downstream component in purple. Note that the beam is delivered through the centre of the upstream device, and the tape is passed through the centre of the downstream device.

The structure that houses GRIFFIN's outer detectors is in six parts, each of which is machined from solid aluminium. There are three main regions of the structure - a corona, an upstream (northern) lampshade and a downstream (southern) lampshade. The corona can hold eight of the 16 HPGe detectors in a ring perpendicular to the beam. The two lampshades, which are mounted on to the side of the corona, each hold four HPGe detectors, at either 45° (downstream) or 135° (upstream) relative to the direction of beam [28]. Each of these three structures comes in two halves, the western and eastern hemispheres. Fig. 2.4 is a visual aid, showing the arrangement of these areas. The two hemispheres can be rolled apart from each other, exposing the detectors (as seen in Fig. 2.2). This allows for maintenance,

alignment and replacement of GRIFFIN's various systems.

2.2.1 Tape system

The radioactive beam is now moved through beamlines into GRIFFIN, where it is incident upon a moving tape system [28]. This tape is widely available, and is composed of a stretched polyester film (Mylar), with one side coated in a thin layer of iron oxide. A continuous loop (approx. 135 m) of this tape is used in GRIFFIN, passing inside the tube of the ancillary downstream detector via a system of rollers. Where the tape reaches the end of the detector, it is held perpendicular to the beamline at a standard distance, so an incoming beam would impinge upon the tape at the centre of the GRIFFIN array. It is important that radioactivity be central to the array, as any significant deviation would create a bias in the angular distribution of emitted gamma-rays (see Chapter 1.2).

By the time the beam is incident upon the tape, it has been slowed to a beam energy of 20 - 40 keV, so that it may penetrate 20 - 100 nm into the tape and be stopped [28]. As such the radioactive ions are implanted into a spot on the tape, with a diameter smaller than 5mm [18]. As the beam continues to fire on that spot, a radioactive source builds.

While the incident beam yield is fairly consistent, the activity of the source building on the tape does not increase linearly. The radioactive isotopes are decaying from the moment they are produced, so even as more parent isotopes are implanted, the half-life of the parent limits the growth of

Figure 2.5: Two examples of growth-decay cycles over the length of a tape cycle. These are for decays of (a) ^{160}Eu and (b) ^{128}Cd . Note the vastly different timescales due to the different half-lives - 380s of implantation in (a), compared to 10s in (b).

activity. After approximately 5 half-lives, the growth and decay of the curve will equilibrate, and reach a point of saturation*. When the beam is turned off, the usual exponential decay curve of radioisotopes is seen, according to the radioactive decay law,

$$N = N_0 e^{-\lambda t}$$

where N_0 is the initial number of parent nuclei, λ is the decay constant, and t is the time elapsed [31].

This saturation effect is shown in Fig. 2.5. An ideal tape cycle would allow the activity to saturate but not remain saturated for more than a few lifetimes, as contaminating daughter activity will also begin to build. As such, the time between tape movements can vary as much as the half-

*The calculation of this value is beyond the scope of this text, but can be found in Ref.[31]

lives themselves. See, for example, the difference between the 380 s ‘beam on’ implantation of ^{160}Eu (Fig. 2.5a) and the 10 s implantation of ^{128}Cd (Fig. 2.5b). These values are derived from the half lives of the respective radioisotopes - 38 s for the former, and 246 ms for the latter.

One of the greatest advantages of a tape system such as this is the ability to move the tape before the activity of any unwanted daughter nuclei begins to build. This allows for very clean spectra, with minimal interference from second or third generation daughters.

2.2.2 HPGe Array

GRIFFIN’s primary array is a set of 16 *High Purity Germanium* (HPGe) detectors, cryogenically cooled with liquid nitrogen to an operating temperature of 95 K. Each detector has four separate crystals - arranged in a clover, as seen in Fig. 2.6 - for a total of 64 crystals. The aluminium casing around the crystals is 1.5 mm thick at the forward-facing side. Each crystal in the clover is 60 mm in width and 90 mm in length. When all 16 clovers are surrounding a source, they are packed very close together in order to cover a greater solid angle (see Fig. 2.2). To accommodate this, the two outside edges of each crystal are tapered at an angle of 22.5° for the first 30 mm of their length [32].

HPGe crystals are used as they have various advantages over other semiconductor γ -ray detectors - such as room-temperature storage, annealing to repair radiation damage, and improved efficiency due to large detection

volumes - discussed in more detail in Appendix A. The most important advantage, however, is their superior energy resolution. When compared to a 3 inch x 3 inch NaI scintillator, the GRIFFIN HPGe array has an average energy resolution of 1.89(6) keV at 1.33 MeV, with an average relative efficiency of 41 % [32].

2.2.3 Ancillary detectors

One of GRIFFIN's greatest strengths is its ability to combine powerful, high-resolution HPGe γ -ray detectors with a tailored selection of other detectors, which are each specialised for a certain type of particle detection. Not all of the detector systems can be used together, but different combinations provide varying spectroscopic perspectives. Which combination is most appropriate for an experiment can be decided on a case-by-case basis.

Figure 2.6: Diagram of a GRIFFIN HPGe clover, with the four crystals coloured for ease of labelling – the actual crystals are not coloured. Figure from Ref. [32].

A brief description of the five main ancillary detectors [28] is provided below.

2.2.3.1 ‘Outer’ detectors

LaBr₃(Ce). The LaBr₃(Ce) system is a set of up to eight scintillating γ -ray detectors, occupying the eight triangular faces of GRIFFIN’s structural geometry (see Fig. 2.3). These detectors have excellent timing resolution [10], which is required for lifetime measurements.

DESCANT. The *Deuterated Scintillator Array for Neutron Tagging* (DESCANT) is a hemisphere of deuterated benzene liquid scintillators, which replaces the downstream lampshade of GRIFFIN, displacing four HPGe clover detectors and four LaBr₃(Ce) detectors. It is used for detecting neutrons in β -delayed neutron emission experiments.

2.2.3.2 ‘Inner’ detectors

SCEPTAR. The *Scintillating Electron-Positron Tagging Array* (SCEPTAR) is a segmented plastic scintillator β particle detector, and has both upstream and downstream components. It is designed to identify electrons from the β decay of a parent nuclei.

PACES. The *Pentagonal Array of Conversion Electron Spectrometers* (PACES) is a set of 5 closely-packed lithium-drifted silicon detectors which can occupy the upstream component of GRIFFIN. PACES is designed to detect internal conversion electrons. This detector requires cryogenic cooling, and so one HPGe detector is displaced to make room for a liquid nitrogen dewar.

ZDS. The *Zero-Degree Scintillator* (ZDS) is a plastic fast β detector, which can occupy the downstream component of GRIFFIN. It is used in conjunction with the $\text{LaBr}_3(\text{Ce})$ detectors for fast-timing measurements.

2.2.4 Data Acquisition System

The GRIFFIN *data acquisition* (DAQ) system was designed to process very high data rates from the HPGe detectors, which requires many hardware modules, whilst keeping the modules synchronized. As such, there are three stages to the signal processing, each a factor of 16 more compact. The hardware for each stage is linked to one of several ‘slave’ clocks. These slave clocks are then synced to a ‘master’ clock, which keeps time consistent through the system. The data collection stages are described briefly here. For more information, see Ref. [33].

The lowest level of data collection is done by the GRIF-16 modules, which convert the signals from HPGe semiconductor detectors into a digital form. Each GRIF-16 module can accept up to 16 channels, which it passes through an *analogue-to-digital converter* (ADC) and to a signal processor. The signal is then passed to the next level of the DAQ.

The middle and top levels are both formed of GRIF-C collector modules. The middle level is a set of up to 16 GRIF-C slave modules, which each concentrate the data from up to 16 GRIF-16 modules into one output.

The data from the 16 GRIF-C slaves is passed to the GRIF-C master module, which is different from the other GRIF-C’s by virtue of its *master filter*.

The master filter is a piece of firmware that applies logic to the incoming data in order to decide whether it should be discarded or written to disk. This prevents the data storage from being overwhelmed with large volumes of unnecessary data in high-rate experiments, but it can be optionally bypassed. These filter conditions are described in greater detail in Ref. [33].

2.3 S1607 Experiment

This γ -ray spectroscopic analysis is performed using data collected during the S1607 experimental campaign, which intended to use the LaBr₃(Ce) detectors' fast timing capabilities to determine the lifetimes of levels in Hg. Even-even isotopes from ¹⁸⁸Hg to ²⁰⁰Hg were studied.

2.3.1 Beam yield and composition

The radioactive beam produced by the ISAC-I facility for this experiment was of exceptional quality. The beam was very pure, as no contaminants were found in the beam. The yield of ¹⁹²Tl was measured at $2.0 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$ – the highest yield of the masses observed in this experimental campaign, which otherwise ranged from $2.8 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $1.6 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

2.3.2 Tape cycling

As stated previously, this experimental campaign was originally proposed to measure the lifetimes of states. As such, some aspects of the setup were not

optimized for HPGe spectroscopy, such as the use of the tape system. As discussed in Chapter 2.2.1, the half-life of the beam isotope determines how long it takes for the implanted source to reach saturation. Unfortunately, the two ^{192}Tl isomers have quite long lifetimes for an implantation experiment – 9.6(4) min and 10.8(2) min respectively [20]. This means that saturation could take upwards of an hour to achieve. Due to the great time investment to build a source, it was decided that no automatic tape cycling would be used. Instead, the source would be left to build and then remain until some practical reason to cycle the tape arose. As a result, any daughter activity that developed would also remain. This was not as problematic for the intended $\text{LaBr}_3(\text{Ce})$ data analysis as it was for the HPGe data analysis, as internal transitions of the daughter contaminants were of far lower energies than the original γ -rays of interest.

Fortunately, ^{192}Hg has a *substantially* longer lifetime than ^{192}Tl , 4.85(20) h, and decays only by electron capture[†]. Therefore, the activity observed from the daughter, ^{192}Au , is quite minimal. Granddaughter contaminants are also very low, as ^{192}Au has a half-life of 4.94(9) h, and decays into stable ^{192}Pt . This decay chain can be seen in Fig. 2.7.

The strongest γ -ray seen in the internal decay of ^{192}Au is the 275 keV γ -ray. That transition is seen in with an intensity of 1.50% relative to the most intense transition in ^{192}Hg . The 275 keV transition occurs in 54% of decays, so the maximum possible daughter contaminant intensity can be calculated

[†]See Chapter 1.3

Figure 2.7: Decay chain of ^{192}Tl to stable ^{192}Pt , with lifetimes. Isotopes are arranged as they would be on the chart of nuclides – Z against N . Data from present literature, Ref. [20]

by the following;

$$I_{max}^{Au} = \frac{I_{275}}{P_{275}} = \frac{1.5\%}{0.54} = 2.78\%$$

where I is intensity of the γ -ray detected, and P is the probability of the transition in a ^{192}Au decay.

This would suggest that any transition with a greater intensity than 2.78% cannot be a daughter contaminant. To further characterize the contaminants, the same procedure can be applied to the internal decay of ^{192}Pt . In this case, the 296 keV transition occurs in 25% of decays and is seen with 0.01% relative intensity. Applying the same formula, the maximum possible intensity of

contaminating granddaughter γ -rays is

$$I_{max}^{Pt} = \frac{I_{296}}{P_{296}} = \frac{0.01\%}{0.25} = 0.04\%$$

2.3.3 Detector arrangement

In this experiment, the inner detectors used were ZDS (downstream) and PACES (upstream). The full LaBr₃(Ce) detector array was installed, as well as 15 of the possible 16 GRIFFIN HPGe clovers. One clover (Position 13) was removed in order to make room for the PACES liquid nitrogen dewar.

Table 2.1: Positions of HPGe detectors in GRIFFIN during this experiment. Distances are measured from the centre of the array. No detector was installed in position 13 during this experiment, as the space was filled by the PACES liquid nitrogen dewar.

Pos.	Dist. (mm)	Pos.	Dist. (mm)
1	113.7	9	110.0
2	114.8	10	110.0
3	112.5	11	110.0
4	115.5	12	110.0
5	110.0	13	-
6	110.0	14	113.3
7	110.0	15	113.5
8	110.0	16	110.0

In addition, six of the 15 HPGe clovers were not positioned at the standard 110 mm distance from the centre of the array (see Table 2.1). These select clovers were pulled back to slightly different distances from the center so as to allow the $\text{LaBr}_3(\text{Ce})$ detectors to be moved closer to the point of implantation. Prioritization of the $\text{LaBr}_3(\text{Ce})$ detectors was reasonable, but caused some unforeseen issues in the analysis of HPGe data. Changing these distances changed the solid angle of the crystals in the detectors, causing a systematic error in the angular correlation analysis – this issue will be described in greater detail in Chapter 3.4.2.2

2.3.4 DAQ issues

At the time of this experiment, the GRIFFIN DAQ was still in development, and as such there were a few small issues. The first version of the GRIF-16 digitizer modules had problems with the ADC components. Due to unexpected problems with their electronics, there was a distinctly non-linear relationship between the charge of the signal from the detectors and the energy of the γ -ray that induced the signal. The increased complication of the relationship between charge and energy meant that a standard polynomial calibration method was not sufficient for this data set. An alternative method was developed, described in Chapter 3.1, that calibrated the 60 HPGe channels effectively.

Chapter 3

Analytical techniques

All analysis in this experiment was conducted using GRSISORT [34], a bespoke analysis software built upon ROOT by CERN [35]. GRSISORT is built and maintained by P. Bender, V. Bildstein and R. Dunlop for use by the GRIFFIN collaboration.

3.1 Calibration

Proper calibration is vital to a successful analysis. As HPGe arrays have such good energy resolution, a poor energy calibration can have a significant impact on the quality of the results. The calibration for this data set was slightly different to the ‘standard’ calibration method, and warrants discussion.

As described in Section 2.2.4, the signal received from the HPGe crystals is analogue - the charge induced by the gamma ray passing through the

Figure 3.1: Comparison of the Akima (solid blue line) and polynomial (dashed red line) fitting procedures. In this case, an unrefined linear calibration has been applied to the data to convert the charge spectrum into an energy spectrum. The chart shows how the difference between the peak energy and literature energy (ΔE) varies with literature energy (E). This example uses Eu-152 data, for an arbitrary crystal.

semiconductor. The charge induced is related to the energy of the incident gamma ray by a simple mathematical equation. This relationship is different for each crystal, and can differ between experiments due to various external influences, so a new calibration must be made for each experiment.

In order to define the charge-energy relationship, data is taken using well-known calibration sources. In this case, ^{60}Co , ^{152}Eu and ^{56}Co were used. The charge spectrum obtained from each crystal is then compared to the

known energy of the gamma rays, therefore obtaining the charge-energy relationship. The equation representing this relationship would, in most cases, be almost linear. A quadratic equation is often sufficient to fit the points with acceptable accuracy. Unfortunately, a technical issue in the ADC modules meant that the charge-energy relationship became more complicated. A standard polynomial relationship would oscillate unrealistically in regions between peaks, but it was found that an *Akima*-type spline* was not as affected by these non-linearities. This is shown in Fig. 3.1.

These non-linearity issues also meant that for regions where there were no reference peaks in the calibration sources, the calibration was poor. The ^{152}Eu source has distinct peaks ranging from 121.8 keV to 1408.0 keV, but there is a region between 344.3 keV and 778.9 keV with no calibration peaks. This is unfortunate, as there are many peaks of interest in the ^{192}Hg spectrum in that region. In order to improve the calibration further (and therefore improve the overall quality of the analysis), it was decided that some distinct and well-known peaks from ^{192}Hg would also be used as calibration peaks - an “internal calibration”. As the precise energies of these γ -rays are not the ultimate goal of this experiment, it was deemed reasonable to use the literature energies of ^{192}Hg peaks for calibration.

The valuable effect of this internal calibration can be seen in Figs. 3.2 and 3.3. In these figures, an ideal calibration would have straight vertical lines

*An Akima spline is a form of spline that uses neighbouring points to find the best fit, rather than the whole data set at once, making it “stable to outliers” [36].

Figure 3.2: Comparison of the calibration in the 600 – 800 keV region using (a) an Akima calibration with standard calibration sources and (b) the previous calibration, refined with a ^{192}Hg Akima. Energy is along the x-axis, crystal number along the y-axis, and number of detected counts along the coloured z-axis. An ideal calibration would have straight vertical lines with minimal variation.

(a) Akima calibration with standard calibration sources.
2D Histogram of array number against energy

(b) The above calibration, refined with a ^{192}Hg Akima calibration.

Figure 3.3: See Fig. 3.2 caption. This figure is a closer look at an individual line - in this case, the most intense gamma-ray, 423 keV.

for each transition with minimal variation, showing that all of the crystals are in agreement. The improvement from the internal calibration is clear. This improvement will be most valuable for previously unknown transitions, for which this may be the first documented observation. This clarity will also mean that especially weak transitions (which a poor calibration would ‘spread out’ and possibly make unresolvable) are more likely to be observed.

The full list of calibration peaks and sources used are given in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Table of all calibration sources used during this experiment, and the peak values that were used in calibration. Values given in the precision used during calibration. Note that the 400 keV to 800 keV region has only one calibration peak that is not from ^{192}Hg . This lack of calibration peaks motivated the choice to use an internal calibration.

Source	Peak (keV)	Source	Peak (keV)
^{152}Eu	121.782	^{152}Eu	964.082
^{192}Hg	174.0	^{152}Eu	1112.080
^{152}Eu	244.698	^{60}Co	1173.24
^{152}Eu	344.279	^{152}Eu	1299.148
^{192}Hg	422.8	^{60}Co	1332.508
^{192}Hg	634.8	^{152}Eu	1408.013
^{192}Hg	745.5	^{56}Co	1771.357
^{152}Eu	778.907	^{56}Co	2034.710
^{192}Hg	786.3	^{56}Co	2598.500
^{152}Eu	867.383	^{56}Co	3253.503

3.2 Simple γ spectroscopy

This investigation of ^{192}Hg involved several stages, and various analytical histograms. First, a spectrum was made containing every ‘good’ gamma-ray event[†] - this will now be referred to as the *singles spectrum*.

The singles spectrum contains $1.4e + 10$ γ -ray detections from 20 keV to 5000 keV. This upper limit was chosen because the Q -value of the electron capture of ^{192}Tl to ^{192}Hg is 6140(35) keV, so there were not expected to be many transitions with energies over 5000 keV. Another factor affecting this is the efficiency of the GRIFFIN HPGe detectors (ϵ); at high energies, the efficiency of the array is very low, so it becomes less probable that an emitted γ -ray at that energy will be detected. The efficiency curve used in this analysis was calculated by A.D. MacLean[‡], and can be seen in Fig. 3.4.

The singles spectrum is unable to provide firm evidence to justify γ -ray transition placements in the level scheme, but it is vital for finding γ -ray *intensities*. This is because the intensity with which a γ -ray is emitted is not equivalent to the intensity with which it is detected. Instead, the area of the peak in singles (A) must be divided by the efficiency of the array (ϵ), where the efficiency is calculated using the centroid energy of the peak (E_γ) in eV.

Therefore, intensity (I) is;

$$I = \frac{A}{\epsilon}$$

[†]That is, not a ‘pile-up’ event. For details regarding pile-up, please see Section 4.4 of Ref. [33].

[‡]University of Guelph, Ontario, Canada

Figure 3.4: Efficiency curve of the GRIFFIN spectrometer during this experiment. Efficiency (ϵ) is plotted against γ -ray energy (E) beyond the maximum Q-value of the ^{192}Tl electron capture decay. Calculated by A.D. MacLean.

where efficiency is;

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon = \exp[& -2.28119 - 0.550598 \ln(E_\gamma) - 0.131461 \ln(E_\gamma)^2 \\ & - 0.212785 \ln(E_\gamma)^3 + 0.061341 \ln(E_\gamma)^4 + 0.115598 \ln(E_\gamma)^5 \\ & - 0.012373 \ln(E_\gamma)^6 - 0.029029 \ln(E_\gamma)^7 - 0.005646 \ln(E_\gamma)^8] \end{aligned}$$

This method is very simple, but can only be used for the singles spectrum. If one was to measure the peak area from a spectrum that had other conditions placed on it, such as coincidence with a certain γ -ray, then you

must account for the efficiency of both γ -rays, as well as various other effects caused by gating and background subtraction. As a result, the intensities quoted in this document will all be from the singles spectrum. There are some gamma-rays for which an accurate peak area could not be found, but this will be addressed in later chapters.

3.3 γ - γ Coincidence

One of the most powerful tools for establishing a nuclear level scheme is γ - γ coincidence analysis. This method is possible with any array that has more than one detection region, so GRIFFIN's powerful HPGe array is more than capable. Building on the introduction to this analytical method provided in Section III.D.1. of Appendix A; an internally decaying nucleus can make several transitions between energy levels as it de-excites. Each transition emits a γ -ray, and so long as the states involved in the transition have negligible (sub-nanosecond) lifetimes, the γ -rays will arrive in the HPGe detectors within a very narrow time window. These γ -rays are *in coincidence*. If two γ -rays are known to exist but are not seen within this time window of each other, then they are not in coincidence and may either be parallel (such as the 745 keV and 786 keV transitions in Fig. 3.5) or otherwise not of the same cascade of transitions. When this coincidence information is found for many γ -rays, then a level scheme can be constructed with great confidence.

Figure 3.5: A partial level scheme of ^{192}Hg , from accepted literature. Note that the 422.8 keV transition is in coincidence with all three of the other transitions, but 786.3 keV and 745.5 keV are parallel, and therefore will not be found in coincidence with each other. Data from ENSDF, Ref. [20]

3.3.1 Creation of γ - γ coincidence spectra

3.3.1.1 Time-random background subtraction

To perform coincidence analysis, one must first establish the aforementioned time window. This is done by taking a small section of the data and plotting the time difference between each of the γ -ray detection events. This produces the histogram shown in Fig. 3.6. The step-like shape of this graph is due to

Figure 3.6: A histogram of the time between hit detections for a subsection of the data. The green line marks the true coincidence region, and the red lines mark the time-random coincidence region. The filled red area indicates the background counts, which is scaled to equate to the orange ‘true’ background region. This subtraction allows for analysis of only the counts in the green region, which are genuine coincident transitions.

both the time resolution of the HPGe detectors and the filtering processes of GRSISORT.

The largest number of counts in this histogram occurs when the time between γ -rays is very small, $\Delta t < 350$ ns. This is the region of *true coincidence*, where the γ -rays that are emitted in the internal decay cascade of the same nucleus. This true coincidence region is delineated by a green line in Fig. 3.6.

However, as well as the true coincidences, there are also random coincidences between γ -rays that are emitted from other decaying nuclei – ^{192}Hg or

otherwise – but just happen to be detected at similar times. These are called *time-random* coincidences, and this is a form of background that must be accounted for in γ - γ coincidence analysis. These random coincidences occur with the same likelihood at any given time interval, hence the constant number of counts in the 500 to 1900 ns range. From a physical perspective, this value should be approximately constant for all time intervals, but instead it begins to drop from 2000 ns onwards due to an automatic filtering process GRSISORT applies – the event building window – which uses a moving 2000 ns time window to discard events without coincidences.

From this small section of data, the time boundaries of true coincidence ($|\Delta t_{true}| \leq 350$ ns) and time-random coincidence (500 ns $\leq |\Delta t_{rand.}| \leq 1900$ ns) were found. When processing the full data set, a 2D histogram of $E_{\gamma,1}$ against $E_{\gamma,2}$ is made for all events that fall into the time-random region, and another for all events that fall into the true coincidence region (including background). The time-random histogram is scaled down by a factor of $\frac{350\text{ns}}{1900\text{ns}-500\text{ns}} = 0.25$, so that it is equivalent to the background contribution in the true coincidence region (i.e. the orange region on Fig. 3.6). Now, by subtracting the scaled background histogram from the true coincidence histogram, a new 2D histogram containing only real internal decay coincidences is found (i.e. the green region on Fig. 3.6). This new *corrected* histogram, shown for the $E_{\gamma,1}, E_{\gamma,2} < 1500$ keV region in Fig. 3.7, is used for the remainder of the γ - γ coincidence analysis.

Figure 3.7: The time-random background corrected 2D histogram for the region $E_{\gamma,1}, E_{\gamma,2} < 1500$ keV. $E_{\gamma,1}$ is on the x-axis, $E_{\gamma,2}$ on the y-axis, and number of counts on the z-axis (represented by colour). Horizontal and vertical lines are candidates for real γ -ray transitions. Diagonal lines are the result of Compton scattering.

3.3.1.2 Compton scattering

A part of the time-random corrected 2D histogram is shown in Fig. 3.7. For context, a vertical yellow line on this histogram would be a peak in a projection on the x-axis. The strong vertical and horizontal lines are all real γ -ray transitions, but the diagonal lines that originate where strong lines meet an axis. These diagonal lines are caused by the Compton scattering of γ -rays, where the γ -ray does not deposit its full energy in the first crystal it impinges upon, and instead scatters into a neighbouring crystal and deposits the remaining energy there. This results in a misleading coincidence between two events that both have some fraction of the energy of the original transition. This can occur for any γ -rays, but for especially intense transitions, this results in a distinct diagonal line across the 2D histogram that can cause problems during analysis. If a coincidence is found between two arbitrary low-intensity peaks, but the sum of their energies is equal to another (usually intense) transition, then care must be taken to make sure that the peaks are real, and not the result of Compton scattering.

3.3.1.3 Coincidence gating

In order to produce a 1D histogram of the coincidences with a specific γ -ray, a GRSISORT tool called TBGSUBTRACTION was used, shown in Fig. 3.8. TBGSUBTRACTION was developed to take the projection of one axis of a 2D histogram (e.g. $E_{\gamma,1}$) and allow the user to select a region corresponding to the peak of interest and up to two background regions. The tool displays the

Figure 3.8: User interface of the TBGSubtraction tool. Labelled regions are; 1) x-axis projection - energy axis that is gated, 1a) peak gate region, 1b) first background region, 1c) second (optional) background region, 2) real-time y-axis projection of the background-subtracted gated region.

1D projection of that peak region on the other energy axis of the histogram, with the background region scaled and subtracted. See Fig. 3.8. Gating regions must be selected carefully so as to remove as much background as possible – it is preferred that at least one background gate is placed at energies lower than the peak energy for Compton background removal. This tool was used to generate 1D coincidence histograms for peaks in the ^{192}Hg spectrum, from which the level scheme was developed.

3.3.2 Analysis of γ - γ coincidence spectra

3.3.2.1 Peak fitting procedure

Once the coincidence spectra have been generated, the γ -ray peaks must be analysed. The area and central value (or centroid) of each peak must be known, with errors. To do this, a RADWARE [37] peak function integrated into the GRSISORT framework was used. The RADWARE function is designed to fit the specific spectroscopic features of γ -rays in a HPGe detector. A χ^2 minimization procedure (see Appendix B) was used to fit the bin content of the histograms with this three-part formula. The three components of this formula are;

- Gaussian – main shape of the peak.
- Skewed Gaussian – low-energy tail due to physical interactions of the HPGe crystal lattice (namely, charge trapping[§]).
- Smoothed step function – reproduces the background ‘step’, a feature of the peaks where the background plateau is higher at the low-energy side than the high-energy.

This fitting procedure minimizes the χ^2 of several parameters in this formula for data in a user-specified energy range (i.e. the peak region). The user can set limits on the values these parameters can take. There are four main parameters that can be limited to ensure a good fit – the height, width

[§]See Ref. [38] for details about charge trapping in semiconductors.

(σ) and centroid of the unskewed Gaussian, and the height of the background step. When fitting a peak that was just composed of one γ -ray transition, the RADWARE peak fitting procedure could be left almost entirely free in order to get the best and most realistic fit. The true advantage of parameter limitation is when fitting a peak that has components from multiple γ -ray transitions - a *doublet* peak.

3.3.2.2 Treatment of doublets

Doublet (or triplet, etc.) peaks are peak regions that are composed of multiple contributing γ -rays. Due to the finite resolution of real detectors, peaks have a finite width, and when the centroid energies of multiple peaks are closer than their width, they overlap. These γ -rays can be untangled in a few ways. To explain this methodology, the 1112.6 keV and 1113.8 keV doublet in ^{192}Hg will be used as an example.

The reader is directed to Fig. 3.9. In the singles spectrum, a prominent peak can be seen at approximately 1113 keV. When this region is observed in two coincidence gates, 423 keV and 619 keV, two peaks of different energies are seen. This reveals that the ‘peak’ in the singles spectrum is actually a doublet, with two overlapping components, 1112.6 keV and 1113.8 keV. As such, the area of the superposed peaks in singles cannot be found by standard peak fitting, so the intensities of the two γ -ray transitions cannot be easily extracted.

In these cases, limiting parameters in the RADWARE peak fitting can

Figure 3.9: Comparison of three partial spectra of the 1100 keV to 1125 keV region. Top, singles spectrum. Middle, 423 keV coincidence spectrum. Bottom, 619 keV coincidence spectrum. Note that while there only appears to be one peak in the singles spectrum, the coincidence gating reveals that there are actually two different γ -ray transitions (1112.6 keV and 1113.8 keV) that are superposed in the singles spectrum.

Figure 3.10: Example of fitting multiple RADWARE peaks. Functions for the 1112.6 keV, 1113.8 keV, 1117.7 keV, 1122.6 keV and 1129.7 keV peaks (which are confirmed to be real through coincidence analysis) have all been considered, resulting in the red ‘total’ function. The dashed red line indicates the background function, which correctly steps downwards in the middle of the 1113 keV region.

help to solve such issues. Multiple RADWARE peaks can be fit to the same data range, with the disadvantage that the fits are much more likely to be unphysical. If the true centroid values of the peaks are known, then the centroid parameter for those peaks can be fixed or limited to a small range. The width of the peak σ is also helpful to limit – because the γ -rays are of very similar energies, the efficiency and resolution of the detectors should be approximately equal, so they should have very similar peak widths. An example of fitting multiple RADWARE peaks can be seen in Fig 3.10, which is constructed of 5 peak functions.

3.4 γ - γ Angular Correlation

The γ - γ angular correlation technique is an analytical method based on the angular distribution of emitted γ -rays (see Chapter 1.2). By finding the probability distribution of the angle between two consecutive γ -rays, conclusions can be drawn about the spins of the nuclear states involved.

The first section will discuss how to produce experimental angular distribution plots from event data. The next section will discuss how that experimental data is compared to theoretical angular distributions to draw conclusions about nuclear structure.

3.4.1 Analysis of experimental data

3.4.1.1 Physical geometry of GRIFFIN

An understanding of the physical geometry of the GRIFFIN spectrometer's detection regions and their relative positions is critical when performing γ - γ angular correlation analysis. Recall that GRIFFIN's rhombicuboctahedral structure, and the clover of crystals at each square face, can be seen in Fig. 2.3. There are 51 unique angles that can be made between the many HPGe crystals, ranging from 18.8° to 180° . It is possible to include a 52nd angle at 0° if the correlation is made between two events in the same crystal, but this is often problematic due to the summing effect[¶], so only 51 angles

[¶]When γ_a and γ_b are incident upon the same crystal at same time, the detector 'sees' a false count at energy $E = E_{\gamma,a} + E_{\gamma,b}$. Further detail can be found in Section 4.1.3 of Ref. [28].

were considered in this analysis.

There are many different pairs of crystals that have the same angular difference between them. For example, within a single clover of crystals in a detector (Fig. 2.6), there are four pairs of crystals with angular difference 18.8° , and two pairs with angular difference 25.6° . The full table of angles and number of pairs with that angular difference can be found in Section 2 of Ref. [18].

If one were to make 2D histograms of all γ - γ coincidences detected in crystals with the same angular difference, then coincident counts for an arbitrary cascade would be affected by several factors. First of all, the counts would be most influenced by the number of pairs contributing to that angle, as an angle with 128 contributing pairs would be approximately a factor of 2 larger than an angle with 64 contributing pairs. This overwhelms the small effect of γ -ray angular distribution. Additionally, the influence of each detectors individual efficiency is not negligible, and must be accounted for. To make these corrections, an *event mixing* technique was applied.

3.4.1.2 Theory of the event mixing technique

The event mixing technique is based in the simple theory that by treating an *isotropic* distribution of γ -rays (i.e the decays of different individual nuclei) in the same way as the *anisotropic* cascading γ -rays, the effect of the different efficiencies can be recreated. The true correlation data can then be normalized using the isotropic data, and the anisotropic nature can be

Figure 3.11: Examples of the stages of the event mixing technique using an arbitrary $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ cascade. In (a) and (b), black circles are true correlation data points, and red squares are event mixed data points. In (a), there are four distinct ‘bands’ because the data is dominated by the number of angle pairs (48, 64, 96 or 128). In (b), the data has been divided by the number of angle pairs, and the clear difference between the true correlation and event mixed data can be seen. In (c), the true data has been normalized using the event mixed data, and the points fall much closer to a parabolic path. Figure from Ref. [18]

revealed. For example, see Fig. 3.11. The true correlation data points (black circles) and event mixed data points (red squares) appear quite similar in part (a) due to the dominating effect of the number of angle pairs. Even just dividing by this number for each of the angles makes the shape of the cascades angular correlations clear, but the fit of the data is still affected by the detector efficiency. The effect of the efficiency fluctuations can be seen in the event mixed data in part (b) – the data should be wholly isotropic, but the points still have some variation. The result of normalization is clear in part (c), where the data falls much closer to a parabolic path than before normalization.

3.4.1.3 Event mixing in practice

There are a number of steps to angular correlation analysis. First, 153 2D histograms must be generated – three for each angle. These histograms have the same axes as the γ - γ 2D coincidence histograms – $E_{\gamma,1}$ on the x-axis, $E_{\gamma,2}$ on the y-axis, counts on the z-axis. For each angle, the histograms generated are;

- **True correlation, true coincidence**, i.e. $|\Delta t| \leq 350$ ns
- **True correlation, time-random coincidence**, i.e. 500 ns $\leq |\Delta t| \leq 1900$ ns
- **Event mixed correlation**, where Δt is “unphysically large” [18], so events cannot be from the same decaying nucleus.

Time-random background subtraction is then performed, as described in Chapter 3.3.1.1. There are now 102 histograms; 51 background-subtracted true correlation histograms (T), and 51 event mixed histograms (EM).

Next, a gate must be made on γ_1 in each of the 102 histograms. These 1D gated spectra are generated in the same way as the γ - γ coincidence spectra, with peak and background gates. The γ_2 peak is fit in each histogram, and the area recorded.

Then, the normalization factor must be calculated. This is calculated as

$$N = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{51} A_{T,i}}{\sum_{i=1}^{51} A_{EM,i}}$$

$$\Delta N = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{51} \Delta A_{T,i}}{\sum_{i=1}^{51} \Delta A_{EM,i}}$$

where A is area, ΔA is the error in area, N is the normalization factor and ΔN is the error in the normalization factor.

Finally, the angular correlation graph can be constructed using

$$C_\theta = \frac{A_{T,\theta}}{N A_{EM,\theta}}$$

and

$$\Delta C_\theta = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta A_{T,\theta}^2}{A_{EM,\theta}^2 * N^2} + \frac{\Delta A_{EM,\theta}^2 * A_{T,\theta}^2}{A_{EM,\theta}^4 * N^2} + \frac{\Delta N^2 * A_{T,\theta}^2}{A_{EM,\theta}^2 * N^4}}$$

where C_θ is the normalized counts for angle θ , and ΔC_θ is the error in that value. Now, an experimental angular distribution can be constructed, which can be compared to theory to determine the spins of the energy levels.

3.4.2 Comparison to theory and extraction of results

3.4.2.1 Parameterization of angular correlation

Chapter 1.2 introduced the theoretical basis of γ - γ angular correlation – that is, that the angular probability distribution $W(\theta)$ can be expressed as

$$W(\theta) = A_{00} [1 + a_2 P_2(\cos \theta) + a_4 P_4(\cos \theta)]$$

where a_2 and a_4 are theoretical angular correlation coefficients, and A_{ii} is a series of coefficients.

Smith *et. al.* [18] propose the definition of three further distributions, denoted Z ,

$$Z_0(\theta) = 1$$

$$Z_2(\theta) = 1 + P_2(\cos \theta)$$

$$Z_4(\theta) = 1 + P_4(\cos \theta) .$$

from which they derive^{||} Z_{sum} , a linear combination of the three, that can be expressed in the form,

$$Z_{sum} \approx N [1 + c_2 P_2 + c_4 P_4]$$

This new distribution can be fit to experimental data using the χ^2 mini-

^{||}To avoid needless repetition, the reader is referred to Ref. [18] for the full, lengthy derivation.

mization technique (Appendix B). The result of this fitting is a set of coefficients, c_2 and c_4 . These are the experimental angular correlation coefficients, but in order to be physically relevant, they must be related to the theoretical coefficients a_2 and a_4 . This is done through parameters β and γ , where

$$c_2 = \beta a_2$$

$$c_4 = \gamma a_4$$

These two parameters, β and γ , have a dependence on the two transition energies, $E_{\gamma,1}$ and $E_{\gamma,2}$, that can be modelled as a surface. This surface must be determined through many GEANT4 simulations [39] of cascades spanning a wide range of energies. This surface has already been determined for the standard experimental setup, and an online tool is available to retrieve these β and γ values, Ref. [40].

By finding the c_2 and c_4 values experimentally and retrieving the appropriate β and γ values from the online tool, the physically significant a_2 and a_4 values can be extracted.

3.4.2.2 Detector arrangement corrections

It was noted in Chapter 2.3.3 that the arrangement of HPGe detectors in GRIFFIN during this experimental campaign was slightly unusual - six of the 15 detectors were held at non-standard distances, slightly further away from the source, so as to allow the LaBr₃(Ce) detectors to be moved closer.

Initially, the common belief was that there would not be any issue per-

forming angular correlation analysis with this non-standard arrangement, as the event mixing technique would account for any changes in efficiency. Unfortunately, as the analysis proceeded, it became clear that there was a systematic error in the results, which is believed to be due to the solid angle of the detectors changing. This may have changed the β and γ parameter surfaces in unexpected ways.

To test this, A.D. MacLean performed a comparison of two simulations, one where the detectors were at the standard distance, and one where they were at the real distances. He simulated a $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ cascade of energies $E_{\gamma,1} = 592$ keV, $E_{\gamma,2} = 413$ keV using GEANT4 simulation software. The results are given in Table 3.2, where β and γ are the parameters described in the previous section, and δ is the mixing ratio of the decay, which represents the contribution of different multipolarities to a transition. The β and γ differences are reflected in the mixing ratio. For a $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ cascade, the mixing ratio should be 0 as they are both pure E2 transitions. As you can see, the ‘standard distance’ simulation was not within error of 0, however the ‘real distance’ simulation was much more accurate. These investigative simulations revealed that GRIFFIN is “extremely sensitive to pulling back the detectors when we have high statistics” (A.D. MacLean, personal communication, October 17, 2019).

Table 3.2: Results of A.D. MacLean’s investigation of the effects of non-standard detector distances. For this example, the δ value should equal zero. Note that when the standard distances were assumed during the simulation, the δ value is not within error of 0, but when the real distances used in this experiment were simulated, the correct results was retrieved.

Param.	Standard	Real
β	0.95275(67)	0.95971(68)
γ	0.84136(87)	0.84289(88)
δ	0.0066(25)	0.0004(25)

This issue *does not invalidate these experimental results*, as the c_2 and c_4 values are still valid. Rather, further intensive simulations will need to be conducted to create bespoke β and γ parameter surfaces for the data collected in this experimental campaign. This work is in motion, and those corrections will be retroactively applied to the work presented here. Until this work is complete, the spins of nuclear energy levels can still be known with the same confidence. Only mixing ratios are considerably affected, and as such, they will not be presented in this work.

Chapter 4

Results and discussion

4.1 γ -rays and γ -ray coincidences

There were many γ -rays that were identified during this analysis. 240 of the γ -rays that were confirmed to be real and resulting from ^{192}Hg can be found in Appendix C. Relative intensities are expressed a percentage of the most intense γ -ray transition, the $2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ transition of $E_\gamma = 422.7$ keV. γ -rays without a stated intensity were unable to be reliably fit in the singles spectrum, either due to overlapping doublet peaks or low intensities. The energies of such γ -rays were found through coincidence gating.

4.2 γ - γ angular correlation results

Each angular correlation analysis produces two graphs - the angular distribution graph and the mixing ratio graph. Both are made by minimizing χ^2/NDF in some way. The former minimizes a curve to the experimental data to retrieve an experimental angular correlation. The latter compares this experimental angular correlation to theoretical curves, evaluated 400 times for different mixing ratios. See Appendix B for more information.

Due to the aforementioned systematic error due to detector arrangement, the error in the normalized counts in each γ - γ angular correlation has been inflated. While many more angular correlations were attempted than those discussed here, the presence of doublet peaks or low statistics often lead to poor results. The following section presents the results of all viable γ - γ angular correlations in this investigation.

4.2.1 422.7 keV and 634.7 keV

In order to confirm the accuracy and reliability of the γ - γ angular correlation techniques in this case, the first cascade analysed was the $4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$, $E_{\gamma,1} = 634.7$, $E_{\gamma,2} = 422.7$. These three levels are the lowest levels of the ground state band, and as such they are known with great certainty. These spin-parity assignments have been confirmed through various experimental methods [20]. Additionally, as this is a $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ cascade, both transitions are purely E2 in character, so their mixing ratio (δ) is zero.

Figure 4.1: γ - γ angular correlation of the 422.7 keV and 634.7 keV γ -rays, from the known cascade $4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$. Black points are the experimental data, and the red line shows the fit to data, using the χ^2 minimization technique.

To investigate this cascade, gates were made on the 422.7 keV γ -ray, and the peak area of the 634.7 keV γ -ray was measured. In this example, the spin of the initial state is being investigated (J_i) and the spins of the intermediate and final states are known ($J = 2$ and $J = 0$, respectively). The result can be seen in the angular distribution graph, Fig 4.1, where the fit to the data has $\chi^2/\text{NDF} = 2.018^*$. From this fit, the experimental angular correlation

*See Appendix. B

Figure 4.2: χ^2/NDF comparison of potential spin assignments for the 422.7 keV and 634.7 keV angular correlation. $J_i = 0$ to 4 are considered, for all mixing ratios. The 99% confidence interval is indicated by a dashed line at $\chi^2/\text{NDF} = 2$. Only $J_i = 4$ is below this confidence interval with $\chi^2/\text{NDF}_{min} = 1.922$. Although $J_i = 2$ appears close, it is not below the confidence interval, with $\chi^2/\text{NDF}_{min} = 2.113$.

parameters were found to be

$$c_2 = 0.101(1) \quad c_4 = 0.007(1)$$

This experimental correlation parabola very closely resembles the theoretical expectation for a $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ cascade, shown in Fig. 1.3, indicating that the methodology used here is reliable. To quantify this qualitative assessment, the reduced χ^2 fit of potential spin assignments (across all possible mixing ratios) were found. This can be seen in the mixing ratio graph, Fig. 4.2, which shows the reduced χ^2 of theoretical spin assignments ($J_i = 0$

to 4) where each spin has been evaluated for all possible mixing ratios δ . The dashed line at $\chi^2/\text{NDF} = 2$ is the 99% confidence interval, and any value with $\chi^2/\text{NDF} > 2$ is excluded as a possible spin assignment. Only the $J_i = 4$ curve meets this threshold, with $\chi^2/\text{NDF}_{min} = 1.922$ at small δ^\dagger . The $J_i = 2$ curve is close to this threshold, with $\chi^2/\text{NDF}_{min} = 2.113$, but is excluded. This analysis demonstrates that the γ - γ angular correlation technique can correctly reproduce known results.

[†]Recall that the mixing ratio results require future corrections, so no specific values will be given here.

Figure 4.3: γ - γ angular correlation of the 745.4 keV and 173.9 keV γ -rays, from the cascade $(7)^- \rightarrow 6_1^+ \rightarrow 4_1^+$. Black points are the experimental data, and the red line shows the fit to data, using the χ^2 minimization technique.

4.2.2 745.4 keV and 173.9 keV

The $J_i \rightarrow 6_1^+ \rightarrow 4_1^+$ cascade of the 1976.7 keV, 1802.8 keV and 1057.4 keV levels ($E_{\gamma,1} = 173.9$, $E_{\gamma,2} = 745.4$) was then analysed. The gates were placed upon the 745.4 keV γ -ray and the peak area of the 173.9 keV γ -ray was measured. The intermediate and final states were fixed and the initial state J_i was investigated. The results can be seen in Figs. 4.3 and 4.4.

The fit to the data in Fig. 4.3 has a reduced $\chi^2 = 2.095$, from which the

Figure 4.4: χ^2/NDF comparison of potential spin assignments for the 745.4 keV and 173.9 keV angular correlation. $J_i = 4$ to 8 are considered, for all mixing ratios. The 99% confidence interval is indicated by a dashed line at $\chi^2/\text{NDF} = 2$. Both the $J_i = 5$ and $J_i = 7$ meet the 99% confidence limit, both with $\chi^2/\text{NDF}_{\min} = 1.978$ at small mixing ratios.

experimental angular correlation parameters were found to be

$$c_2 = -0.064(2) \quad c_4 = 0.001(2)$$

The χ^2/NDF against δ plot for this correlation does not exclusively determine a spin for the initial state, as both $J_i = 5$ and $J_i = 7$ have $\chi^2/\text{NDF}_{\min} = 1.978$ at small mixing ratios, meeting the 99% confidence limit. Arguments in Chapter 4.3.2 will assign the spin of the initial state as $J_i = 7$, so this result will be able to provide a mixing ratio for the 173.9 keV transition, once corrections are available.

Figure 4.5: γ - γ angular correlation of the 634.7 keV and 786.3 keV γ -rays, from the cascade $J_i \rightarrow 4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$. Black points are the experimental data, and the red line shows the fit to data, using the χ^2 minimization technique.

4.2.3 634.7 keV and 786.3 keV

In the analysis of the $J_i \rightarrow 4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$ cascade of the 1843.7 keV, 1057.4 keV and 422.7 keV levels ($E_{\gamma,1} = 786.3$ keV and $E_{\gamma,2} = 634.7$ keV), gates were placed upon the 634.7 keV γ -ray and the peak area of the 786.3 keV was measured. The intermediate and final states were fixed and the initial state J_i was investigated. The results can be seen in Figs. 4.5 and 4.6.

The fit to the data in Fig. 4.5 has a reduced $\chi^2 = 1.856$, from which the

Figure 4.6: χ^2/NDF comparison of potential spin assignments for the $J_i \rightarrow 4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$ angular correlation, 634.7 keV and 786.3 keV. $J_i = 2$ to 6 are considered, for all mixing ratios. The 99% confidence interval is indicated by a dashed line at $\chi^2/\text{NDF} = 2$. $J_i = 3, 5$ and 7 all meet the 99% confidence limit, with $\chi^2/\text{NDF}_{\min} = 1.977, 1.957$ and 1.749 respectively.

experimental angular correlation parameters were found to be

$$c_2 = -0.077(2) \quad c_4 = 0.008(3)$$

The χ^2/NDF against δ plot for this correlation does not exclusively determine a spin for the initial state, as $J_i = 3, 5$ and 6 all meet the 99% confidence limit. Arguments in Chapter 4.3.2 will assign the spin of the initial state as $J_i = 5$, so this result will be able to provide a mixing ratio for the 786.3 keV, once corrections are available.

Figure 4.7: γ - γ angular correlation of the 786.3 keV and 343.0 keV γ -rays, from the cascade $J_i \rightarrow (5)^- \rightarrow 4_1^+$. Black points are the experimental data, and the red line shows the fit to data, using the χ^2 minimization technique.

4.2.4 786.3 keV and 343.0 keV

In the analysis of the $J_i \rightarrow (5)^+ \rightarrow 4_1^+$ cascade of the 2186.7 keV, 1843.7 keV and 1057.4 keV levels ($E_{\gamma,1} = 343.0$ keV and $E_{\gamma,2} = 786.3$ keV), gates were placed upon the 786.3 keV γ -ray and the peak area of the 343.0 keV was measured. The intermediate and final states were fixed and the initial state J_i was investigated. The results can be seen in Figs. 4.7 and 4.8.

The fit to the data in Fig. 4.7 has a reduced $\chi^2 = 1.527$, from which the

Figure 4.8: χ^2/NDF comparison of potential spin assignments for the $J_i \rightarrow (5)^- \rightarrow 4_1^+$ angular correlation. $J_i = 3$ to 7 are considered, for all mixing ratios. The 99% confidence interval is indicated by a dashed line at $\chi^2/\text{NDF} = 2$.

experimental angular correlation parameters were found to be

$$c_2 = 0.309(5) \quad c_4 = -0.002(7)$$

Strangely, the implications of this coincidence are that the 2186.7 keV state is a $J = 4$ state but this state decays to $J = 5, 6$ and 7 states. A $4 \rightarrow 7$ decay is incredibly unlikely due to γ -ray transition laws, especially as this transition is very low energy.

This angular correlation result, of the ones presented here, is most susceptible to the parameter errors. This is because the mixing ratio of the 'known' transitions in each analysis must be fixed. For the other analyses,

this fixed mixing ratio must be zero as they are pure E2 transitions, and was fixed as such. For this analysis however, the mixing ratio could not be determined through the 634.7 keV-786.3 keV correlation analysis, as it requires corrections. For the purposes of the 786.3 keV-343.0 keV analysis, the mixing ratio of 786.3 keV was fixed at zero, but this has not yet been thoroughly confirmed. As such, this result is the most liable to change when corrections are available, and so this investigation does not completely exclude the more probable $J = 6$ assignment, especially as its minimum χ^2 value is so close to the 99% confidence interval.

Figure 4.9: γ - γ angular correlation of the 422.7 keV and 1112.6 keV γ -rays, from the cascade $(3)^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$. Black points are the experimental data, and the red line shows the fit to data, using the χ^2 minimization technique.

4.2.5 422.7 keV and 1112.6 keV

In the analysis of the $J_i \rightarrow 2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ cascade of the 1535.0 keV, 422.7 keV and 0.0 keV levels ($E_{\gamma,1} = 1112.6$ keV and $E_{\gamma,2} = 422.7$ keV), gates were placed upon the 422.7 keV γ -ray and the peak area of the 1112.6 keV was measured. The intermediate and final states were fixed and the initial state J_i was investigated. The results can be seen in Figs. 4.9 and 4.10.

The fit to the data in Fig. 4.9 has a reduced $\chi^2 = 2.040$, from which the

Figure 4.10: χ^2/NDF comparison of potential spin assignments for the $(3)^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ angular correlation. $J_i = 0$ to 4 are considered, for all mixing ratios. The 99% confidence interval is indicated by a dashed line at $\chi^2/\text{NDF} = 2$. Both $J_i = 3$ and 4 meet the 99% confidence limit, with $\chi^2/\text{NDF}_{\min} = 1.936$ and 1.937 respectively.

experimental angular correlation parameters were found to be

$$c_2 = 0.226(5) \quad c_4 = -0.047(7)$$

The χ^2/NDF against δ plot for this correlation does not exclusively determine a spin for the initial state, as $J_i = 3$ and 4 both meet the 99% confidence limit at large δ .

4.3 Proposed updated level scheme

The γ -rays identified in the internal decay of ^{192}Hg are shown in Fig. 4.11. Transitions known in the current literature are shown in black, and new results from this analysis are shown in red.

As doublet peaks are some of the most difficult to confidently place in a level scheme, the following chapter will describe the various arguments for the doublet placements. Some components do not have firm placements – in such cases, efforts have been made to describe what other transitions the component is in coincidence with, so as to provide future experiments a basis from which to expand.

4.3.1 Placing of doublet peaks

4.3.1.1 1112.6 keV and 1113.8 keV

This doublet was known to exist in previous experiments, but their individual energies were not known.

1113.8 keV: 1113.6 keV \rightarrow 0.0 keV

This γ -ray is quite a unique situation, in that it is not in coincidence with the 422.7 keV, but is seen in singles. This implies that it feeds the ground state, which agrees with one of the previously known assignments. Therefore, this γ -ray is placed firmly.

1112.6 keV: 1535.0 keV \rightarrow 422.7 keV

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV but not 634.7 keV, or any γ -rays

Figure 4.11: Proposed level scheme for ^{192}Hg . The width of the transitions represents relative intensity. Transitions in black were previously known, transitions in red are new results from this analysis.

feeding 634.7 keV. This implies it is parallel, i.e. feeding the 422.7 keV state. This agrees with one of the previously known assignments. If placed feeding the 422.7 keV state, the energy of this transition would imply a state at 1535.0 keV, which is a known state. Therefore, this γ -ray is placed firmly.

4.3.1.2 690.7 keV, 692.6 keV and 694.3 keV

690.7 keV: 1113.6 keV \rightarrow 422.7 keV

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV but not 634.7 keV implying it is parallel, i.e. feeding the 422.7 keV state. It is also in coincidence with 619.2 keV, a γ -ray that feeds the 1113.6 keV state - but not the 1113.8 keV out of that state. Taken together, this firmly places the 690.7 keV transition between the 1113.6 keV and 422.7 keV states.

692.6 keV: 2536.3 keV \rightarrow 1843.7 keV

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV, 634.7 keV and 786.3 keV, but not 745.4 keV, 132.9 keV or 173.9 keV, implying it feeds the 1843.7 keV state. If placed feeding the 1843.7 keV state, the energy of this transition would imply a state at 2536.3 keV, which is supported by the next doublet assignment, 733.5 keV. Therefore, this γ -ray is placed firmly.

694.3 keV: Unassigned

This γ -ray is very weak, and is overwhelmed in almost every coincidence gate by the other two components of this triplet. It is only visible in the 1112.6 keV and 1113.8 keV coincidence gates, because neither of the other components are in coincidence with them. As such, this γ -ray is known to

exist, but cannot be placed.

4.3.1.3 731.9 keV and 733.5 keV

733.5 keV: 2536.3 keV \rightarrow 1802.8 keV

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV, 634.7 keV and 745.4 keV but not 786.3 keV, implying it feeds the 1802.8 keV state. If placed feeding the 1802.8 keV state, the energy of this transition would imply a state at 2536.3 keV, which is supported by the previous doublet assignment, 692.6 keV. Therefore, this γ -ray is placed firmly.

731.9 keV: Unassigned

This γ -ray is very weak, and is overwhelmed in almost every coincidence gate by the 733.5 keV. It is only visible in the 690.7 keV gate, as the 733.5 keV is not in coincidence with this γ -ray. The fact that this γ -ray is in coincidence with 690.7 keV but none of the transitions above it could imply that this is a 1845.4 keV \rightarrow 1113.6 keV transition but, as this is a very weak γ -ray and cannot be seen in either 1113.8 keV or 587.8 keV, such a placement would be very uncertain.

4.3.1.4 675.3 keV and 676.3 keV

675.3 keV: 1732.7 keV \rightarrow 1057.4 keV

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV, 472.4 keV, 397.3 keV, 397.3 keV, 534.9 keV and 634.7 keV. It is not in coincidence with the 745.4 keV or 786.3 keV, implying it is parallel, i.e. feeding the 1057.4 keV state. If placed

feeding the 1057.4 keV state, the energy of this transition would imply a state at 1732.7 keV, which is a known state. Therefore, this γ -ray is placed firmly.

676.3 keV: 2652.9 keV \rightarrow 1976.6 keV

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 132.9 keV, 173.9 keV, 422.7 keV, 634.7 keV, 745.4 keV and 786.3 keV - the whole chain up to the 1976.6 keV level, but no transitions above that, implying the 676.3 keV transition may feed this level. If placed feeding the 1976.6 keV state, the energy of this transition would imply a state at 2652.9 keV, which is a known state. Therefore, this γ -ray is placed firmly.

4.3.1.5 714.0 keV, 716.4 keV, 718.1 keV and 720.5 keV

This region of the ^{192}Hg spectrum is very crowded, with four quite weak transitions within 6 keV of each other. All are known to exist, assigning firm placements is difficult. The most consequential of these transitions is the 718.1 keV transition, but efforts were made to assign tentative placements for the other components.

718.1 keV: 1831.7 keV \rightarrow 1113.6 keV

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV, 690.7 keV and 796.1 keV, but not 634.7 keV or 774.1 keV. This would imply it is a transition between the already established 1831.7 keV and 1113.6 keV levels. This would be a more tentative assignment were it not for the coincidence with the only known γ -ray feeding the 1831.7 keV (796.1 keV). With that evidence, the γ -ray is placed firmly.

714.0 keV: Tentative, unknown \rightarrow 1802.8 keV

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV, 634.7 keV and 745.4 keV but no others. This would imply that the transition is feeding the 1802.8 keV level, but as there is no known level at 2516.8 keV for it to decay from, this is a tenuous assumption. As this is such a weak transition, in a quadruplet, it could easily be the case that the 714.0 keV γ -ray has more coincidences, but the peak is too small to be seen. Bare in mind that, as the 422.7 keV, 634.7 keV and 745.4 keV transitions are all very intense, coincidence gates on these peaks have more statistics than, for example, the 643.9 keV transition. As such, the 714.0 keV is tentatively ascribed as feeding the 1802.8 keV level somehow, but its origin is not known, and it is excluded from the level scheme.

720.5 keV: Tentative, unknown \rightarrow 2130.2 keV

This γ -ray is obscured in 422.7 keV, but in coincidence with 619.2 keV, 634.7 keV, 675.3 keV and 397.3 keV. This would imply that the γ -ray feeds the 2130.2 keV level, but there is no otherwise known level at 2850.7 keV for it to decay from and these coincidences are not enough evidence for a firm assignment, especially for a γ -ray in such a 'crowded' region. As such, the 720 keV γ -ray most likely feeds the 2130.2 keV in some way, but it is not assigned as a direct transition to the level, and is excluded from the level scheme.

716.4 keV: Unassigned

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV and 1112.6 keV, but there are no other clear coincidences. Therefore, this γ -ray remains unassigned.

4.3.1.6 477.3 keV and 480.3 keV

477.3 keV: 1535.0 keV \rightarrow 1057.4 keV

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV and 634.7 keV, but not 745.4 keV, 786.3 keV, or any other γ -ray feeding the 1057.4 keV state. If this transition is placed directly above the 1057.4 keV state, then it would imply an initial state of 1535.0 keV, which is a known state. Therefore, this γ -ray is placed firmly.

480.3 keV: Unassigned

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 132.9 keV, 323.4 keV 422.7 keV, 634.7 keV, 745.4 keV, 786.3 keV. These coincidences would seem to imply a feeding of the 2300.2 keV state, but without coincidences with the other possible cascade routes from that level, and with no previously known state at the implied initial energy of 2780.5 keV, this transition cannot be firmly assigned.

4.3.1.7 383.9 keV and 384.8 keV

383.9 keV: 2186.7 keV \rightarrow 1802.8 keV

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV, 634.7 keV and 745.4 keV, but not 786.3 keV or any γ -rays feeding the 1802.8 keV level. If the 383.9 keV were feeding the 1802.8 keV level, that would imply it decays from a SI2186.7 state, which is a known state. Therefore, this γ -ray is placed firmly.

384.8 keV: Unassigned

This γ -ray is quite weak, and is only observed individually in the 643.9 keV coincidence gate, as the 383.9 keV does not appear in that spectrum. As

such, no transition can be firmly assigned for this γ -ray.

4.3.1.8 557.5 keV and 559.5 keV

557.5 keV: 2402.8 keV \rightarrow 1845.4 keV

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV and 1422.7 keV, and not 634.7 keV, 690.7 keV or any other transitions to the 422.7 keV. This implies a decay to the 1845.4 keV state from 2402.8 keV, which is a known state. Therefore, this γ -ray is placed firmly.

559.5 keV: Unassigned

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 132.9 keV, 173.9 keV, 422.7 keV, 634.7 keV, 745.5 keV and 786.3 keV. This could imply a decay into the 1976.6 keV state from a 2536.1 keV state, but as no other evidence of such a state exists, this would be an unreasonable assumption. As such, this γ -ray remains unassigned.

4.3.1.9 1418.8 keV and 1422.7 keV

1422.7 keV: 1845.4 keV \rightarrow 422.7 keV

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV but not 634.7 keV, 690.7 keV or any other transitions feeding the 422.7 keV state. This implies that the γ -ray feeds the 422.7 keV state directly, placing a level at 1845.4 keV. There are two additional levels built upon this 1845.4 keV level that have other confirmed decays, lending more support to this placement – this γ -ray is placed firmly.

1418.8 keV: Unassigned

This γ -ray is in coincidence with 422.7 keV and 634.7 keV, but no others. If this γ -ray directly fed the 1057.4 keV state, it would imply a state at 2475.4 keV. As there is no other evidence of such a state, this placement would be tenuous, and the γ -ray remains unassigned.

4.3.2 Spin assignments

Through these results, several conclusions can be drawn. First, the 1976.6 keV state – previously a tentative 7^- – can be assigned. The 1976.6 keV state decays to a firmly assigned 6^+ state (in the ground state band). Through γ -ray decay laws, this implies that the state most likely has spin $J = 4, 5, 6, 7$ or 8 . The γ - γ angular correlation for the 745.4 keV and 173.9 keV transitions excludes $J = 4, 6$ and 8 , leaving $J = 5$ or 7 . As this state does not populate the 4_1^+ state, this implies that the state cannot be $J = 5$. This is because the large energy difference between the states would make such a decay energetically favourable, so if it were an allowed decay, it should be seen. As it is not, then a $J = 5$ state can be ruled out. Therefore, the 1976.6 keV can be firmly assigned as $J = 7$. This assignment is further supported by a concurrent investigation of this data set by my colleague C. Cheng, looking at γ - e coincidences to determine the multipolarities of decays. Her work is yet to be published, but assigns the transition to the 6^+ state as E1 in character, further confirming the spin-parity of this state as $J = 7^-$.

Next, the 1843.7 keV state – previously a tentative 5^- – can be assigned. The 1843.7 keV state decays to a firmly assigned 4^+ state (in the ground

state band) Through γ -ray decay laws, this implies that the state most likely has spin $J = 2, 3, 4, 5$ or 6 . The γ - γ angular correlation for the 634.7 keV and 786.3 keV transitions excludes $J = 2$ and 4 , leaving $J = 3, 5$ or 6 . As there is also a transition between this state and the newly-confirmed 7^- state, this excludes a $J = 3$ assignment. The angular correlation result cannot distinguish between the $J = 5$ or 6 states, but as before, C. Cheng's work assigns this transition as E1 in character. This firmly assigns the 1843.7 keV state as $J = 5^-$.

As before, energy arguments can be made for the 1535.0 state that assign possible spin values of $J = 2, 3$ or 4 . Angular correlations of the 422.7 keV and 1112.6 keV transitions exclude $J = 2$, leaving $J = 3$ or 4 as possible assignments.

4.3.3 Table of levels and transitions

Table 4.1: Table of the levels and transitions in ^{192}Hg , with new transitions marked with an asterisk (*). The table is arranged by the energy of the initial level (E_i), with its assigned spin (J_i). For each transition from that level, the energy of the γ -ray (E_γ) and its relative intensity as a percentage of the most intense transition (Rel. I) is provided. The energy and spin assignment of final state of the transition is also given (E_f and J_f , respectively.)

E_i (keV)	J_i	E_γ (keV)	Rel. I (%)	E_f (keV)	J_f
422.7(1)	2_1^+	422.7(1)	100.00(1)	0.0(1)	0_1^+
1057.4(1)	4_1^+	634.7(1)	92.02(1)	422.7(1)	2_1^+
1113.6(1)	(1, 2)	690.7(1)	2.97(1)	422.7(1)	2_1^+
		1113.8(1)	0.97(1)	0.0(1)	0_1^+
1535.0(1)	(3, 4)	1112.6(1)	2.97(1)	422.7(1)	2_1^+
		477.3(1)	— — —	1057.4(1)	4_1^+
1732.7(1)	(2, 3, 4, 5, 6)	619.2(1)	1.78(1)	1113.6(1)	(1, 2)
		675.3(1)	2.42(1)	1057.4(1)	4_1^+
1802.8(1)	6_1^+	745.4(1)	34.11(1)	1057.4(1)	4_1^+
1831.7(1)	(2, 3, 4)	718.1(4)	— — —	1113.6(1)	(1, 2)
		774.1(1)	1.05(1)	1057.4(1)	4_1^+
		* 1409.2(1)	0.04(1)	422.7(1)	2_1^+
1843.7(1)	5_1^-	786.3(1)	37.67(1)	1057.4(1)	4_1^+
1845.4(1)	(3, 4)	1422.7(1)	0.77(1)	422.7(1)	2_1^+
1909.9(1)	(1, 2)	1487.2(1)	— — —	422.7(1)	2_1^+
		1909.9(1)	0.06(1)	0.0(1)	0_1^+

1976.6(1)	7_1^-	132.9(1)	7.04(1)	1843.7(1)	5_1^-
		173.9(1)	14.24(1)	1802.8(1)	6_1^+
2056.9(1)	(0, 1, 2, 3, 4)	1634.2(1)	0.14(1)	422.7(1)	2_1^+
2082.1(1)	(0, 1, 2, 3, 4)	1659.4(1)	0.14(1)	422.7(1)	2_1^+
2110.1(1)	(0, 1, 2, 3, 4)	* 1687.4(1)	— — —	422.7(1)	2_1^+
2130.2(1)	(2, 3, 4, 5, 6)	* 397.3(1)	1.01(1)	1732.7(1)	(2, 3, 4, 5, 6)
		* 595.2(1)	0.60(1)	1535.0(1)	(3, 4)
		* 1073.0(1)	— — —	1057.4(1)	4_1^+
2186.7(1)	(4, 6)	* 210.0(1)	0.56(1)	1976.6(1)	7_1^-
		343.0(1)	2.76(1)	1843.7(1)	5_1^-
		383.9(1)	3.07(1)	1802.8(1)	6_1^+
2215.9(1)	(5, 6, 7, 8, 9)	239.2(1)	4.99(1)	1976.6(1)	7_1^-
2223.8(1)	(9)	247.1(1)	2.69(1)	1976.6(1)	7_1^-
2267.9(1)	(2, 3, 4, 5, 6)	* 534.9(1)	0.55(1)	1732.7(1)	(2, 3, 4, 5, 6)
		* 1210.8(1)	2.02(1)	1057.4(1)	4_1^+
2300.1(1)	(5, 6, 7)	323.4(1)	3.35(1)	1976.6(1)	7_1^-
		* 456.5(1)	1.01(1)	1843.7(1)	5_1^-
		* 497.4(1)	— — —	1802.8(1)	6_1^+
2402.8(1)	(2, 3, 4, 5, 6)	* 557.5(3)	— — —	1845.4(1)	(3, 4)
		* 1345.4(1)	1.04(1)	1057.4(1)	4_1^+
2433.3(1)	(2, 3, 4, 5, 6)	* 1376.0(1)	0.92(1)	1057.4(1)	4_1^+
		* 587.8(1)	0.18(1)	1845.4(1)	(3, 4)

2446.7(1)	8 ⁺	643.9(1)	1.96(1)	1802.8(1)	6 ₁ ⁺
2536.3(1)	(4, 5, 6, 7)	* 692.6(1)	1.69(1)	1843.7(1)	5 ₁ ⁻
		* 733.5(1)	1.44(1)	1802.8(1)	6 ₁ ⁺
2602.6(1)	(4, 5, 6, 7, 8)	* 334.7(1)	0.28(1)	2267.9(1)	(2, 3, 4, 5, 6)
		* 472.4(1)	1.28(1)	2130.2(1)	(2, 3, 4, 5, 6)
		* 799.9(1)	0.10(1)	1802.8(1)	6 ₁ ⁺
2628.3(1)	(2, 3, 4, 5, 6)	* 796.5(1)	0.21(1)	1831.7(1)	(2, 3, 4)
		* 1571.1(1)	— — —	1057.4(1)	4 ₁ ⁺
2652.9(1)	(5, 6, 7, 8, 9)	* 437.0(1)	0.25(1)	2215.9(1)	(5, 6, 7, 8, 9)
		* 676.3(1)	— — —	1976.6(1)	7 ₁ ⁻
2800.7(1)	(5, 6, 7, 8)	* 824.0(1)	0.78(1)	1976.6(1)	7 ₁ ⁻
		* 998.0(1)	0.18(1)	1802.8(1)	6 ₁ ⁺
2844.1(1)	(3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9)	* 544.0(1)	1.03(1)	2300.1(1)	(2, 3, 4, 5, 6)
		* 657.4(1)	0.84(1)	2186.7(1)	(4, 6)
2846.4(1)	(0to8)	* 578.2(1)	0.11(1)	2267.9(1)	(2, 3, 4, 5, 6)

Chapter 5

Conclusions

5.1 Results of this investigation

Previous investigations of the electron capture decay of ^{192}Tl to ^{192}Hg [12] [13] [14] successfully constructed a level scheme for the low-energy low-spin structure which was comprised of 21 energy levels, with 31 transitions between them, and a total of 74 γ -rays resulting from this decay. The investigation presented here has expanded that knowledge base greatly. In this work, 240 γ -rays from ^{192}Hg have been identified, from which an additional 28 previously unobserved transitions have been found.

Great effort was made to correctly place the components of doublet or triplet γ -rays in this nucleus, as this knowledge can be incredibly useful for future experiments. For example, if one were to be interested in the 690.7 keV transition, then they now know that the γ -ray peak is a doublet

with a 692.6 keV transition, higher in the level structure. They would also be able to determine a coincidence condition (e.g. only accept events that are in coincidence with a 619.2 keV γ -ray) that could exclude the 692.6 keV from their analysis, as the position of the doublet in the level scheme is known. This process has been conducted for nine such sets of peaks - future experiments involving ^{192}Hg will benefit from these efforts.

Angular correlation analyses have been performed, and their results have firmly assigned spin states for previously tentative levels. These results have also excluded possible spin assignments from certain levels. While the first excited 0^+ state has not been identified, several candidates (i.e. 2056.9 keV, 2082.1 keV and 2110.1 keV) were found during the γ - γ coincidence spectroscopy. Unfortunately, no γ - γ angular correlation could be performed to identify these states, as their depopulating γ -rays were very weak, and the statistics were too poor for results to be extracted.

The fact that a 0_2^+ state was not observed in such a high-statistics experiment with as powerful an array as GRIFFIN is an interesting outcome in and of itself. There could be several reasons for this; perhaps the 0_2^+ state is not well populated, so the depopulating transitions would be very weak. It could be the case that the 0_2^+ state has a dramatically higher or lower energy than was expected and predicted by theory. It could also simply mean that the depopulating γ -ray is a doublet with a more intense transition, making it difficult to identify and place – this is not unlikely, as the expected energy for this $0_2^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$ transition is in the 700 keV to 1000 keV range, which is a

densely populated region. As such, alternative experimental techniques are recommended in order to locate the interesting (but thus far, elusive) first excited 0^+ state.

5.2 Future work

Further efforts to identify the 0_2^+ state would be well-placed, as ^{192}Hg remains the only even-even isotope of Hg for which the 0_2^+ is not known. As this experiment was unable to identify this state, I would recommend future experimenters to explore alternative experimental techniques (such as those explored in Section III of Appendix A) which may populate different levels. This could help to eliminate a possible doublet transition, or to more heavily populate the 0_2^+ .

Even within this experimental campaign, there is more work to be done. Similar investigations of this kind are already underway for some of the other isotopes observed during this experimental campaign – all even-even isotopes from ^{188}Hg to ^{200}Hg . When these analyses are completed, this work can be placed into a wider context – a systematic view of the low-lying levels of Hg, allowing the changes in nuclear structure across the isotopic chain to be traced. Alongside the recent Hg lifetime measurements made by B. Olaizola *et al.* (2019) [10], this information could improve the accuracy of a future IBM-CM-type theoretical investigation of shape coexistence in Hg.

Overall, while this investigation has revealed more about the low-lying

structure of ^{192}Hg , there is far more that can be learned. This isotope – lying between the shape coexisting region of the midshell and the normal configuration of the closed shell – has far more to reveal about both.

Bibliography

- [1] Bing-Nan, L. et al. “Potential energy surfaces of actinide and transfermium nuclei from multi-dimensional constraint covariant density functional theories”. In: *EPJ Web of Conferences* 38 (2012), p. 05003. DOI: 10.1051/epjconf/20123805003. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/20123805003>.
- [2] T. Otsuka and Y. Tsunoda. “The role of shell evolution in shape coexistence”. In: *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* 43.2 (Jan. 2016), p. 024009. DOI: 10.1088/0954-3899/43/2/024009. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1088/0954-3899/43/2/024009>.
- [3] K. Matsuyanagi et al. “Microscopic derivation of the quadrupole collective Hamiltonian for shape coexistence/mixing dynamics”. In: *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* 43.2 (Jan. 2016), p. 024006. DOI: 10.1088/0954-3899/43/2/024006. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1088/0954-3899/43/2/024006>.
- [4] K. Heyde and J.L. Wood. “Shape coexistence in atomic nuclei”. In: *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 83 (4 Nov. 2011), pp. 1467–1521. DOI: 10.1103/

RevModPhys.83.1467. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/RevModPhys.83.1467>.

- [5] N. Bree et al. “Shape Coexistence in the Neutron-Deficient Even-Even $^{182-188}\text{Hg}$ Isotopes Studied via Coulomb Excitation”. In: *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 112 (16 Apr. 2014), p. 162701. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.112.162701. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.112.162701>.
- [6] L. P. Gaffney et al. “Shape coexistence in neutron-deficient Hg isotopes studied via lifetime measurements in $^{184,186}\text{Hg}$ and two-state mixing calculations”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 89 (2 Feb. 2014), p. 024307. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.89.024307. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.89.024307>.
- [7] K. Nomura, R. Rodriguez-Guzmán, and L.M. Robledo. “Shape evolution and the role of intruder configurations in Hg isotopes within the interacting boson model based on a Gogny energy density functional”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 87 (6 June 2013), p. 064313. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.87.064313. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.87.064313>.
- [8] J.E. Garcia-Ramos and K. Heyde. “Nuclear shape coexistence: A study of the even-even Hg isotopes using the interacting boson model with configuration mixing”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 89 (1 Jan. 2014), p. 014306.

DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.89.014306. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.89.014306>.

- [9] Walter Pfeifer. “An Introduction to the Interacting Boson Model of the Atomic Nucleus, Part I”. In: (Oct. 2002).
- [10] B. Olaizola et al. “Shape coexistence in the neutron-deficient lead region: A systematic study of lifetimes in the even-even $^{188-200}\text{Hg}$ with the GRIFFIN spectrometer at TRIUMF”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 100 (2 Aug. 2019), p. 024301. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.100.024301. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.100.024301>.
- [11] C. Müller-Gatermann et al. “Shape coexistence in ^{178}Hg ”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 99 (5 May 2019), p. 054325. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.99.054325. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.99.054325>.
- [12] R.F. Petry, R.A. Naumann, and J.S. Evans. “Levels in Even-Even Hg^{192} , Hg^{194} , Hg^{196} , and Hg^{198} ”. In: *Phys. Rev.* 174 (4 Oct. 1968), pp. 1441–1454. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRev.174.1441. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRev.174.1441>.
- [13] T.B Vandlik et al. “Decay of the isotopes ^{192}Tl and ^{190}Tl ”. In: *Yad. Fiz.* 22 (5 Nov. 1975), pp. 873–885.
- [14] D.C. Sousa et al. “Radioactive decay of mass-separated ^{192}Tl and ^{192}Pb ”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 24 (5 Nov. 1981), pp. 2245–2259. DOI: 10.1103/

- PhysRevC.24.2245. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.24.2245>.
- [15] R Neugart et al. “Collinear laser spectroscopy at ISOLDE: new methods and highlights”. In: *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* 44.6 (2017), p. 064002. DOI: 10.1088/1361-6471/aa6642.
- [16] E. L. Brady and M. Deutsch. “Angular Correlation of Successive Gamma-Rays”. In: *Phys. Rev.* 78 (5 June 1950), pp. 558–566. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRev.78.558. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRev.78.558>.
- [17] Kenneth S Krane. *Introductory nuclear physics*. New York, NY: Wiley, 1988. URL: <https://cds.cern.ch/record/359790>.
- [18] J.K. Smith et al. “Gamma–gamma angular correlation analysis techniques with the GRIFFIN spectrometer”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 922 (2019), pp. 47–63. ISSN: 0168-9002. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2018.10.097>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168900218314116>.
- [19] K.S. Krane. *Modern Physics, 3rd Edition*. Wiley, 2012. ISBN: 9781118210093. URL: <https://books.google.nl/books?id=3tobAAAAQBAJ>.
- [20] Coral M. Baglin. “Nuclear Data Sheets for A = 192”. In: *Nuclear Data Sheets* 113.8 (2012), pp. 1871–2111. ISSN: 0090-3752. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nds.2012.08.001>.

- [//doi.org/10.1016/j.nds.2012.08.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nds.2012.08.001). URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0090375212000579>.
- [21] *TRIUMF — History*. URL: <https://www.triumf.ca/home/about-triumf/history>.
- [22] *A FEW QUICK FACTS ABOUT THE TRIUMF CYCLOTRON*. June 2019. URL: <https://cycops.triumf.ca/cycfac.htm>.
- [23] *Main Cyclotron Beam Lines*. URL: <https://www.triumf.ca/research-program/research-facilities/main-cyclotron-beam-lines>.
- [24] “Assets: Physical and Intellectual Infrastructure”. In: *TRIUMF Five-Year Plan 2015-2020*. TRIUMF, 2013.
- [25] C. Geppert et al. “Resonance Ionization Laser Ion Source - Off-line tests at TRIUMF”. In: *Nuclear Physics A 746* (2004). Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference on Radioactive Nuclear Beams (RNB6), pp. 631–634. ISSN: 0375-9474. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nuclphysa.2004.09.113>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S037594740401070X>.
- [26] J. Lassen et al. “Current developments with TRIUMF’s titanium-sapphire laser based resonance ionization laser ion source”. In: *Hyperfine Interactions* 238.1 (Feb. 2017), p. 33. ISSN: 1572-9540. DOI: [10.1007/s10751-017-1407-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10751-017-1407-9). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10751-017-1407-9>.

- [27] P. Kunz et al. “Nuclear and in-source laser spectroscopy with the ISAC yield station”. In: *Review of Scientific Instruments* 85 (2014), p. 053305. DOI: <https://doi-org.ezproxy.library.ubc.ca/10.1063/1.4878718>.
- [28] A.B. Garnsworthy et al. “The GRIFFIN facility for Decay-Spectroscopy studies at TRIUMF-ISAC”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 918 (2019), pp. 9–29. ISSN: 0168-9002. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2018.11.115>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168900218317662>.
- [29] Daniel Yates. “Decay spectroscopy of europium-160”. PhD thesis. University of British Columbia, 2019. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.14288/1.0380440>. URL: <https://open.library.ubc.ca/collections/ubctheses/24/items/1.0380440>.
- [30] Nikita Bernier. “Decay spectroscopy of neutron-rich cadmium around the $N = 82$ shell closure”. PhD thesis. University of British Columbia, 2018. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.14288/1.0376019>. URL: <https://open.library.ubc.ca/collections/ubctheses/24/items/1.0376019>.
- [31] Institute of Power Engineering. *Activation and Decay of Radioactive Nuclides*. English. Technische Universität Dresden. 20 pp. March 2015.

- [32] U. Rizwan et al. “Characteristics of GRIFFIN high-purity germanium clover detectors”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 820 (2016), pp. 126–131. ISSN: 0168-9002. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2016.03.016>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168900216300341>.
- [33] A.B. Garnsworthy et al. “The GRIFFIN data acquisition system”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 853 (2017), pp. 85–104. ISSN: 0168-9002. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2017.02.040>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168900217302243>.
- [34] Vinzenz Bildstein et al. “GRIFFINCollaboration/GRSISort: Yappy Yak”. In: (Oct. 2019). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3520949.
- [35] I. Antcheva et al. “ROOT — A C++ framework for petabyte data storage, statistical analysis and visualization”. In: *Computer Physics Communications* 180.12 (2009). 40 YEARS OF CPC: A celebratory issue focused on quality software for high performance, grid and novel computing architectures, pp. 2499–2512. ISSN: 0010-4655. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2009.08.005>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0010465509002550>.

- [36] A. Pichandi et al. “Analysis of physical parameters and determination of inflection point for Flattening Filter Free beams in medical linear accelerator”. In: *Reports of Practical Oncology Radiotherapy* 19 (Sept. 2014). DOI: 10.1016/j.rpor.2014.01.004.
- [37] D.C. Radford. *RadWare Software Package*. Apr. 22, 1998. URL: <https://radware.phy.ornl.gov/>.
- [38] Amy A. Cordones and Stephen R. Leone. “Mechanisms for charge trapping in single semiconductor nanocrystals probed by fluorescence blinking”. In: *Chemical Society Reviews* 42.8 (2013), p. 3209. DOI: 10.1039/c2cs35452g.
- [39] S. Agostinelli et al. “Geant4—a simulation toolkit”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 506.3 (2003), pp. 250–303. ISSN: 0168-9002. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-9002\(03\)01368-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-9002(03)01368-8). URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168900203013688>.
- [40] J.K. Smith. *GRIFFIN Angular Correlation Coefficients*. 2018. URL: <https://griffincollaboration.github.io/AngularCorrelationCoefficients/>.
- [41] R. R. Harris and G. K. Kanji. “On the Use of Minimum Chi-Square Estimation”. In: *J. Royal Stat. Soc. D* 32.4 (1983), p. 379. DOI: 10.2307/2987540.

- [42] Karl Pearson F.R.S. “X. On the criterion that a given system of deviations from the probable in the case of a correlated system of variables is such that it can be reasonably supposed to have arisen from random sampling”. In: *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science* 50.302 (1900), pp. 157–175. DOI: 10.1080/14786440009463897.
- [43] J. Neyman. “Contribution to the Theory of the superscript 2 Test”. In: *Proceedings of the [First] Berkeley Symposium on Mathematical Statistics and Probability*. Berkeley, Calif.: University of California Press, 1949, pp. 239–273. URL: <https://projecteuclid.org/euclid.bsmsp/1166219208>.

Appendix A

Literature Review and Interim Report

Review of the current literature regarding low-lying structures in the nucleus of ^{192}Hg

C.E. Paxman

*Department of Physics, University of Surrey, Guildford GU2 7XH, United Kingdom
TRIUMF, Wesbrook Mall, Vancouver, British Columbia V6T 2A3, Canada*

July 30, 2019

Abstract

A discussion of nuclear deformations and the methods used to investigate such structures is framed around an investigation of the current literature regarding the low-lying, low-spin states of the ^{192}Hg nucleus, accessible by electron capture decay. There are three papers that have used gamma spectroscopy to examine such states – Sousa *et al.* (1981), Vandlik *et al.* (1975) and Petry *et al.* (1968) – which are the main interest of this review. The limitations and conflicts between the three are discussed, and a need for a modern experimental analysis is established. Alternative methods of analysing the structure of nuclei are acknowledged, and their advantages and disadvantages are identified. The methods of obtaining excited nuclei, and the various detectors used to observe them, are examined. To provide context for these works, two current theoretical models of ^{192}Hg are compared, and attention is drawn to the potential future of more detailed theoretical calculations. This literature review is written with the intent of contextualizing and motivating an upcoming thesis on the gamma ray spectroscopy analysis of ^{192}Hg , performed using the GRIFFIN array at TRIUMF, Canada.

Contents

I. Introduction	1
I.A. Nuclear shapes	1
I.B. Shape coexistence	2
I.C. Interest in ^{192}Hg	3
II. Theoretical background	5
II.A. The interacting boson model	5
II.A.1. IBM-2 study of ^{192}Hg	5
II.A.2. IBM-1 (with configuration mixing) study of ^{192}Hg	6
II.B. Monte-Carlo shell model calculations	7
III. Experimental techniques	8
III.A. Production of beam	8
III.B. Methods of excitation	8
III.B.1. Beam implantation experiments	8
III.B.2. Fusion-evaporation experiments	9
III.B.3. Coulomb excitation experiments	9
III.C. Detectors	9
III.C.1. Semiconductor: Ge(Li), HPGe and Si(Li)	9
III.C.2. Scintillator: LaBr ₃ (Ce)	11
III.D. Analysis techniques	11
III.D.1. Gamma ray spectroscopy	11
III.D.2. Gamma-gamma fast timing technique	12
IV. Previous works	13
IV.A. Level schemes of low-lying states	13
IV.A.1. Petry	13
IV.A.2. Vandlik	13
IV.A.3. Sousa	13
IV.A.4. Comparison	14
IV.B. Transition strengths of low-lying states	18
IV.B.1. Esmaylzadeh	18
IV.B.2. Olaizola	18
IV.B.3. Comparison	18
IV.B.4. Coulomb excitation; an alternative technique	20
V. Summary	20
VI. Conclusions	22
VII. Acknowledgements	22

List of Figures

1	Models of nuclear shape deformations.	1
2	Diagram of particle-hole monopole interactions affecting energy levels.	1
3	Modelled potential energy surface of ^{186}Pb , exhibiting triplet states	2
4	Energy level scheme of $^{172-206}\text{Hg}$, showing the normal and intruder levels	3
5	The current literature level scheme of low-lying ^{192}Hg states	4
6	Comparison of IBM-2 and experimental energy levels	5
7	Comparison of IBM-CM and experimental energy levels	7
8	Comparison of MCSM magnetic and quadrupole moment calculations with experimental observation	7
9	Diagram of the fusion-evaporation process.	10
10	A partial level scheme of ^{192}Hg	12
11	Example of Petry <i>et al.</i> 's ^{192}Hg spectra	14
12	Petry <i>et al.</i> 's proposed level scheme	14
13	Vandlik <i>et al.</i> 's proposed level scheme	15
14	Sousa <i>et al.</i> 's proposed level scheme	16
15	Example of Sousa <i>et al.</i> 's ^{192}Hg spectra	17
16	Comparison of Esmaylzadeh <i>et al.</i> 's experimental B(E2) values to theoretical calculations.	19
17	Example of Esmaylzadeh <i>et al.</i> 's HPGe (blue) and LaBr (red) singles spectra for ^{192}Hg	19
18	Comparison of Olaizola <i>et al.</i> 's B(E2) values of the $2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ and $4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$ transitions to literature and theory	20

List of Tables

1	Comparison table of experimental B(E2) values for even-even $^{188-200}\text{Hg}$.	23
---	---	----

I. INTRODUCTION

Our understanding of the nucleus has evolved greatly from early ‘hard sphere’ models to our present, more nuanced picture of protons and neutrons, composing a finite many-body quantum system [1] that is, for heavy nuclei, too complex to be fully described by a single mathematical model. Theoretical models instead require “a drastic truncation scheme” [2] that limits the complexity of the model – the number of nucleons, how they can excite etc. – as we are often unable to precisely predict the effects of intricate nuclear interactions. Through the combined work of experimental observation and theoretical prediction, nuclear structure physicists have come to discover and describe a phenomenon called shape coexistence, which seems to be present in all but the lightest nuclei, and can have drastic effects on the energy level structure of a nucleus. This review aims to introduce the topic of shape coexistence and the experimental techniques used to probe nuclear structure, framed around a discussion of the isotope ^{192}Hg .

I.A. Nuclear shapes

Atomic nuclei are not, as we once believed, strictly spherical objects. The last half-century has seen an emergence of various static deformed eigenstates of nuclei, where nucleon-nucleon interactions drive the overall distribution of nucleons to be non spherically uniform. The nucleus can take several shapes, some of which are shown in Fig. 1. The three most common – and most relevant to this discussion – are spherical, prolate (like a rugby ball) and oblate (like a curling stone); Figs. 1a, b and c respectively. These shapes are defined by their deformation parameter, $\beta_{\lambda\mu}$, a measure of deviation from spherical symmetry. λ represents the multipolarity of the deformation ($\lambda = 1$ for dipole, $\lambda = 2$ for quadrupole, etc.). μ is the projection of λ , and takes values $\mu = -\lambda \dots +\lambda$. The magnitude of this value reveals the ‘strength’ of the deformation, and the sign represents the shape. Prolate and oblate deformations are both *quadrupole* deformations. Prolate shapes have positive $\beta_{\lambda\mu}$, and oblate shapes have negative $\beta_{\lambda\mu}$.

Specifically, the interaction deforming the nucleus

Figure 1: A model of *theoretical* nuclear shapes. From the top left in a clockwise direction: spherical; prolate spheroid; oblate spheroid; hexadecapole; asymmetric octupole (with very large quadrupole deformation); tetrahedron; symmetric octupole; triaxial ellipsoid. Spherical, prolate and oblate are the most commonly observed. Figure from Ref. [3].

is the *coupling* of the quadrupole moment of protons and neutrons, described in great depth in Takaharu Otsuka’s 2016 [4] and 2018 [5] papers. This process can occur through the excitation of protons or neutrons, but this explanation will assume neutron excitation for clarity. In brief, if a neutron is excited, there is a ‘hole’ in the orbital that it would usually occupy in an equivalent, ground-state nucleus (see Fig. 2). The monopole interactions of the neutron particle-hole pairs drive the proton shells together; generally, neutron holes lower the energy of

Figure 2: Diagram of neutron particle-hole monopole interactions affecting proton energy levels. Closed (open) circles denote neutron particles (holes). Wavy lines indicate monopole interactions. Partial figure from Ref. [4]

Figure 3: A theoretical model of the potential energy surface of ^{186}Pb . Three minima are observed, which have been observed to be three different shape deformations, indicated by black lines. $\beta_2 \sin(\gamma + 30)$ and $\beta_2 \cos(\gamma + 30)$ express elongation along an axis. Figure from Ref. [6].

the higher-spin (J) proton orbit, and neutron particles raise the energy of the lower-spin (J) proton orbit [4]. This often causes ‘intruder states’ – states that have lowered in energy relative to the spherical shape, and intrude into the structure of the states below it. These changes in the nuclear orbital energies cause a redistribution of nucleons, which leads to shape deformation.

These excitations can occur in multiples of two. In such cases, the intrinsic spins of the particles can still oppose each other, and the overall spin of the nucleus remains the same, i.e. a spherical 0^+ state can undergo a four particle, four hole (4p-4h) excitation and still be in a 0^+ state, but with deformed shape and higher energy.

I.B. Shape coexistence

These deformed shapes are interesting in and of themselves, but recent research into nuclear shapes is driven by the observation of two or more shape states at close energies [7]. When these states are close together, quantum state mixing can occur [8]. In most cases, only two of these shapes will coexist, but in some rare instances, three can manifest at very close energies, as seen in Fig 3. These low-lying, intruding states tend to emerge gradually along isotopic (constant Z) and isotonic (constant N) chains, with maximal coexistence occurring near the midshell.

As can be seen in Fig. 4, there are reasonably ‘flat’ states at $A = 190$ to 198 , indicated by blue squares, that lie in a band built on the 0^+ ground state. These are the yrast states; the lowest-energy state with that spin assignment, i.e. the lowest 2^+ state, 2_1^+ . There is also a second band of levels that follow a parabolic curve across isotopes (indicated by red circles), reaching a minimum at around $A = 182$, near the neutron midshell. This parabolic curve is evidence of a secondary structure, whose lowest excited state (0_2^+) can fall close to – or sometimes even below – the 2^+ state of the ground state band. These are the aforementioned intruder states, and are an indication of shape coexistence. The 0_2^+ state is the ‘bandhead’ for the intruder states – the other intruder states are built upon it. As such, identification of the 0_2^+ states in each isotope is crucial for an understanding of shape coexistence across the isotopic chain.

Despite this, simply looking at the energy of the states does not make comment on the shape or properties of the secondary structure, and is by no means a thorough proof. For example, conclusions about the shape of 2_1^+ and 2_2^+ states based *solely* on systematic trends would be incorrect at $A = 182$, as the two states appear to ‘swap’, due to the complex nature of the system. Further experiments, such as Coulomb excitation experiments (as described in Section III.B.3.), must be performed to determine the quadrupole deformation parameters β_2 and make conclusions about shape of the states.

Figure 4: An energy level scheme for even-even (even Z , even N) $^{172-206}\text{Hg}$ isotopes. Blue squares indicate normal configuration states, with spherical or weakly deformed shape. Red circles indicate the intruder configuration, with more deformed shape (which is oblate, in this case [9]). Figure from Ref. [10].

I.C. Interest in ^{192}Hg

Mercury, with an atomic number of $Z = 80$, lies just two protons below the magic number $Z = 82$, an area which has “the most extensive manifestation of shape coexistence known anywhere on the nuclear mass surface” [1]. Through the combined efforts of experimentalists and theorists, the $^{176-190}\text{Hg}$ region was identified as exhibiting signs of shape coexistence, and has been thoroughly studied as a result. Interestingly, ^{192}Hg — lying between the midshell region of shape-coexisting structures and the closed-shell region without shape coexistence — has not been studied with the same interest. While recent effort has been made to determine lifetimes of the known states in ^{192}Hg [11][12], no excited 0^+ state has been identified, and many of the observed low-lying energy levels have uncertain spin-parity assignments, such as the 2_2^+ , 3_2^+ and 4_2^+ (see Fig. 5). Although there is often a temptation to discount such isotopes as uninteresting due to their placement just outside of the region of coexistence, this does not hold true under scrutiny. This

isotope presents an opportunity to study the ‘normal’ configuration of nucleons in this region, without the added complications of the intruder configuration and the interband transitions (between bands) that result from it. It could also be argued — as I will do here — that having a fuller understanding of the isotopes in this transitory stage between shape coexisting and non-coexisting isotopes is not only important for scientific rigor, but also to provide greater constraints on theoretical models. Historically, “the important interplay between experimental observation and theoretical description” [1] has been key to advancing our understanding of shape coexistence, and as such, it is “critical to determine the extent of the deformed configurations in these Hg isotopes” [13] on the edges of coexistence. Filling the gaps in our experimental results, such as ^{192}Hg , is a valuable exercise for producing a robust model of the processes behind this phenomenon.

This review is intended to accompany a study of the ^{192}Hg nuclear structure, through gamma-gamma (γ - γ) coincidence and angular correlation analysis. In that study, ^{192}Hg nuclei are populated through the electron capture (EC) decay of ^{192}Tl - these techniques are detailed in Section III.. The immediate goal of that work is to provide a detailed, modern level scheme that identifies new nuclear states, particularly the 0_2^+ , and assigns their spins and parities. This would have a broader impact of completing the systematics of 0_2^+ levels in the neutron-deficient Hg isotopes, allowing for improved constraint/comparison for theoretical models of the isotopes.

With this study in mind, the present review will discuss the current theoretical descriptions and experimental data regarding the ^{192}Hg isotope. There are two main theoretical studies that include the ^{192}Hg isotope, and their methodology and results will be compared in Section II.. The implications of a recent development in theoretical modelling will also be touched upon, although the paper does not directly discuss ^{192}Hg (Section II.B.). A brief review of experimental equipment (Section III.C.) and methods (Section III.D.) will provide context for the experimental studies discussed in Section IV.. The primary focus will be on on decay spectroscopy and γ - γ

Figure 5: The current literature level scheme of low-lying ^{192}Hg states. Bracketed spin-parity assignments and dashed transition arrows are tentative. Red transition lines have intensity > 10% of the most intense transition, 422.8 keV. Level scheme from Ref. [14].

coincidence (Section III.D.1.) as a method of determining energy level structure and spin-parity assignment. Lifetime and CoulEx analyses of ^{192}Hg will be approached in Section IV.B..

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Nuclei are complex, many-body systems and as such, creating robust mathematical models is supremely difficult. There are many ways of approaching this problem, each with their own advantages. In this section, two widely-accepted mathematical methods that have been applied to the Hg isotopic chain, and specifically to ^{192}Hg , are discussed. These two studies – by Nomura *et al.* [2] and García-Ramos & Heyde [15] – are often cited in works on this isotope. Exciting theoretical developments in the $^{177-185}\text{Hg}$ range [16] will also be explored, as they may open the door into the next stage of powerful theoretical modelling.

II.A. The interacting boson model

The Interacting Boson Model (IBM) is a powerful tool for the study of nuclei. It incorporates aspects of the shell model, with refinement from collective models to account for interactions such as the nucleon pairing effect [17]. For even-even isotopes, the IBM simplifies a nucleus into an inert core, and any remaining nucleons are put into identical pairs, represented as bosons. The bosons — as they are two coupled, identical nucleons with an intrinsic spin of 1 — can be described as having angular momentum of $I=0,2$ and positive parity. There are methods that treat protons and neutrons as indistinguishable (IBM-1), or unique (IBM-2). These simplifications lead to multi-dimensional Hamiltonian equations, for which the variables must be somehow constrained. The two studies discussed here, Nomura *et al.* and García-Ramos & Heyde, approach this constraint in different ways.

Figure 6: Comparison energy level diagrams of $^{172-204}\text{Hg}$; (a) IBM-2 theoretical calculation, compared to (b) experimental observation (accurate for 2013). Blue squares indicate normal configuration states, red circles indicate intruder configuration states. Figure from Ref. [2].

II.A.1. IBM-2 study of ^{192}Hg

In the 2013 paper by Nomura *et al.* (2013) [2], the even-even Hg isotopes between ^{172}Hg and ^{204}Hg were studied using the IBM-2 modelling technique. This study aimed to start from a purely theoretical basis, and from there, find “energy levels, deformation properties ... and the ground state properties” of the isotopes they modelled. Their method of constraining the Hamiltonian variables is independent and self-contained; they use an energy density function (EDF) called the Gogny-EDF [18] to map the deformation energy surface of the nucleon. By comparing the Hamiltonian from IBM-2 to this surface, they derived the IBM parameters for the isotopes in their range. Their calculated energy levels, compared to available experimental data of the time, is shown in Fig. 6.

Nomura *et al.* place strong restrictions on their model, so that it would be feasible within the limitations of their computational power. One of these limitations, criticised by Müller-Gatermann *et al.* [19], is the restriction of excitations to two-particle two-hole (2p-2h) proton excitations. Neutron excitations are excluded from the calculation completely, although more recent studies have suggested (Ref. [16]) that the population of the neutron midshell may play a

key role in shape coexistence. The practical effect of this is fixing the number of bosons (nucleon pairs) active in the model to $N_{proton} = 1$ for 0p-0h configurations and $N_{proton} = 3$ for 2p-2h configurations. The number of neutron bosons ($N_{neutron}$) is determined by the number of neutrons not accounted for by the inert core, i.e. ^{172}Hg has $N_{neutron} = 5$ and ^{174}Hg has $N_{neutron} = 6$. These limits succeed in making the simulations possible with the computers available to them, but this trade is not without consequence.

The study makes predictions that cannot be reconciled with experiment, such as the inversion of the prolate intruder and weakly-deformed oblate ground state levels for $^{180-184}\text{Hg}$, or the inaccurate 0_2^+ energy levels around the $A = 182$ parabolic minima. As higher spin states are approached, the model begins to break down – the parabolic shape of the intruder states distorts and is lost for yrast states of $J_{pi} > 6^+$. The non-yrast states are overall less consistent with literature, and do not show a clear parabolic shape. In many cases, the Gogny-EDF surface is identified as the issue — with this kind of purely theoretical calculation, “derived without any fit to the data”[2], the results are “rather sensitive to the choice of the underlying EDF”[19].

The model breaks down for yrast levels at $A > 200$, but this is an intrinsic limitation of the IBM, not just this study. The IBM “excludes pure spherical configurations”, but the ground state band in these isotopes exhibits a spherical nature. This would suggest the use of a different theoretical model to tackle Hg isotopes closer to stability.

Given the limitations, the predictions made are satisfactory – the energy predictions of yrast states $J^\pi \leq 6^+$ match the experimental data, and exhibit a clear parabola. The general trends of the intruding states are seen, but with much less accuracy, and without any indication of a parabola. Most importantly for this review, they predict the “disappearance of the prolate minimum in ^{192}Hg ”, indicating that shape coexistence does not occur in this isotope.

II.A.2. IBM-1 (with configuration mixing) study of ^{192}Hg

The IBM-1 model, which makes no distinction between protons and neutrons, is applied to the even-even $^{172-200}\text{Hg}$ isotopes by García-Ramos & Heyde (2014) [15]. A slightly modified version of the IBM-1 is used, in which *configuration mixing* between different particle-hole excitations is allowed (abbreviated to IBM-CM). In contrast to Nomura *et al.*, this study uses existing experimental data to restrain the parameters of the Hamiltonian.

Starting from the full, 13-variable IBM-CM Hamiltonian, assumptions and constraints are applied to fix variables until 7 free parameters remain. Each isotope’s energy spectrum is calculated by using the MINUIT package [20] to minimise a χ^2 function, which quantifies the error between expected (measured) and calculated (theoretical) values, to find the set of parameters that most closely reproduces the experimental data. For the full derivation and details of the method, see Ref. [15]

The issue with incorporating experimental data in to theoretical models is that, in many cases, the experimental data is incomplete. For example, García-Ramos & Heyde found that they could not calculate two of the variables for $^{190-194}\text{Hg}$, and instead had to assume it to be equal to the equivalent variable of ^{188}Hg , meaning that for those nuclei, two of the seven variables were incorrect by some unknown error. Fortunately, the range for which these parameters were unknown actually seems to follow a fairly simple increasing trend so the assumption is not unreasonable, but $^{192,194}\text{Hg}$ are likely to be less accurate than ^{190}Hg .

The findings of García-Ramos & Heyde are compared to the experimental data of the time in Fig 7 – the close resemblance between the two is immediately apparent. It is important to note that the 2_1^+ energy level was used to constrain the Hamiltonian, so those levels match perfectly. For the 2_2^+ and 2_3^+ , the replication is still very close, and predictions are made in regions where no experimental data had yet been taken which have since been found to be accurate (Section IV.B.). The calculated levels tend to become less accurate for higher-spin non-yrast states, and there is an unexplained systematic error in odd-J

Figure 7: Comparison energy level diagrams of $^{172-200}\text{Hg}$; (a) experimental observation (accurate for 2014), compared to (b) IBM-CM theoretical calculation. Colours indicate spin-parity, shown in the key. Figure from Ref. [15].

states. Despite this the general parabolic trend is far clearer than in Nomura’s calculations.

II.B. Monte-Carlo shell model calculations

The Monte-Carlo Shell Model (MCSM) has not been applied to ^{192}Hg , but it would be remiss of any review to discuss theoretical modelling without a mention of the recent MCSM calculations performed for neutron-deficient $^{177-186}\text{Hg}$.

MCSM calculations apply the basic tenet of any Monte Carlo method - random selection - to a nucleus, in an attempt to solve the quantum many-body problem. These calculations, like IBM calculations, function by taking an inert core and then modelling the various interactions and excitations of the remaining nucleons, but this method is much better at handling large model spaces, with many more ‘free’ (valence) nucleons and “drastic excitations” [21]. A true mathematical description of this method can be found in Otsuka (2001) [21], but a brief overview is provided here. The first step of the MCSM is to select the ‘basis states’ (which are the valence nucleons). Generally, more basis states lead to more accurate results, but it will also require exponentially more

computational power. Once the states are selected, the Hamiltonian matrix is calculated, which provides information about the energy of various states. From this, properties of the nuclear Hilbert space (the generalised form of standard 3-dimensional Euclidean space) can be found.

The results of a MCSM study of $^{177-186}\text{Hg}$ have been published in both Nature by Marsh *et al.* (2018) [16] and Phys. Rev. C by Sels *et al.* (2019) [22]. This groundbreaking research has performed “the heaviest MCSM calculations so far” [22], with the “largest model spaces to date” [16]. They selected a ^{132}Sn inert core, allowing for the interaction of 30 protons and 15-24 neutrons. Recalling standard orbital notation,

Figure 8: Comparison of experimental magnetic (μ) and quadrupole (Q) moment values (red circles) with MCSM calculations (blue rectangles) for odd- A $^{177-185}\text{Hg}$. ‘gs’ indicates ground state. ‘m’ indicates isomeric state. Figure from Ref. [22].

the nucleons could occupy 11 proton (π) orbitals from $\pi g_{7/2}$ to $\pi i_{13/2}$ and 13 neutron (ν) orbitals $\nu h_{9/2}$ to $\nu j_{15/2}$ [16]. Proton-proton, proton-neutron, and neutron-neutron interactions were all allowed. Such large-scale and complex interactions were calculated using the K supercomputer at RIKEN.

As Fig. 8 shows, the known magnetic moments μ and quadrupole moments Q are very closely reproduced in this study. Overall, the model matches experimental findings incredibly closely. The importance of this development cannot be overstated, because this theoretical model does not just provide support for existing experimental values, it can *identify* which proton and neutron orbitals were responsible for deformations. Through this work, the paper concludes that in their simulations, the monopole interaction between the $\nu i_{13/2}$ and $\pi h_{9/2}$ orbitals caused their energies to be lowered. This caused “enhanced occupation” [22] of these levels, which in turn drove the prolate deformation of the nucleus. Given the close agreement between these simulations and experimental observation, it is feasible that this is the process that drives the deformation of real Hg nuclei in this range.

The scope of this study does not extend to ^{192}Hg , but it represents a milestone in theoretical modelling techniques. Such results are promising, and with the operation of the the successor to the K supercomputer - *Fugaku* - expected to commence in 2021, intensive modelling techniques such as the MCSM will become more feasible, which may be critical to the future of theoretical nuclear structure.

III. EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

There are several ways of investigating nuclear structures through experiment, each of which provides information about a piece of the puzzle which, when taken together, can be used to more fully understand the nucleus.[1].

III.A. Production of beam

Many experimental nuclear methods rely on having a beam of accelerated nuclei of a very specific type, often a specific isotope and isomer of an element. To produce this final beam, first an accelerated beam of ions or particles is used to bombard a thin target material, which produces a range of different isotopes through various nuclear reactions. This accelerated beam could be from a cyclotron [23] or tandem linear [24] accelerator. Different target materials and initial beams can be used to produce different varieties of isotope. An on-line isotope separator (ISOL) can be used to select the desired isotope by bending the beam using a magnetic field. The curvature of the bending is dependent upon the isotope’s charge, mass, and the applied magnetic field such that $r_{bend} \propto mv/qB$, so nuclei with different charge-mass ratios can be separated and selected by their ‘magnetic rigidity’; $Br_{bend} \propto mv/q$. [25]. This can produce a final beam of isotopes with few contaminants. Further selection methods can be used to create even purer beams, or to preferentially populate certain metastable isomers [12] (‘long-lived’ excited states) in the nucleus. It is possible to produce a radioactive ion beam (RIB), though the half-life of the isotope can greatly limit the intensity of the beam [26].

III.B. Methods of excitation

III.B.1. Beam implantation experiments

In beam implantation experiments, *decays* are used to populate excited states of nuclei. A beam of (parent) isotopes is incident upon a collector, often aluminized Mylar tape, into which the isotopes are implanted. The implanted parent nuclei can decay through many methods (α , $\beta^{+/-}$, EC etc.) into daughter nuclei of experimental interest, often in an excited state. These excited nuclei will then de-excite, emitting γ -rays and electrons. The emissions can be detected by arrays of different detector types placed around the collector.

This review will focus on electron capture (EC) decay, in which the nucleus absorbs an orbital electron, which combines with a proton to produce a neutron

and a neutrino. In this decay, the states populated in the daughters are limited by the spin-parity of the parent isomers, and the difference of the binding energies of the two nuclei. As such, it tends to populate select spin states that are close to the parent isomer spin (often low-spin), and often cannot access high-energy states. It does not preferentially populate either yrast or non-yrast states.

III.B.2. Fusion-evaporation experiments

Fusion evaporation reactions occur when a beam of projectile nuclei is fired at a target of heavier nuclei. When a projectile and target nucleus make contact, they fuse into a new compound nucleus. In order to fuse, the energy of the incoming projectile must be high enough to overcome the Coulomb barrier, else it will be deflected away.

Through the emission of γ -rays, protons, neutrons and α particles, the unstable compound nucleus can decay into a more stable “evaporation residue” nucleus – this is the nucleus of interest. From here, the nucleus can decay into its ground state through γ and electron emission. These emissions can be collected by detector arrays, and the spectra analyzed. The spectra can have significant background peaks due to the compound nucleus decaying in ways other than evaporation, such as fission (see Fig. 9), and from the production of other evaporation residues.

This method preferentially populates the high-spin, yrast structures in the nucleus.

III.B.3. Coulomb excitation experiments

Coulomb excitation (CoulEx) experiments populate nuclear levels not through radioactive decay, but through inelastic collisions of projectile and target nuclei. By firing the projectile beam with energies *below* the Coulomb barrier, or at certain ‘safe’ angles defined by the Klein-Nishina equation [27], then the nuclei can only interact through inelastic collision, which is a product only of the well-understood electromagnetic force. Any contribution from the more nebulous nuclear forces can be ignored.

These studies are difficult to perform as, to study unstable nuclei, a radioactive ion beam (RIB) must

be used. While “the last years have seen significant progress in the production of RIB” [28], there are still far fewer facilities that can provide low-contamination RIB at high intensity, than can produce a similar quality of *stable* beam.

CoulEx populates levels very selectively, as it builds from the ground state upwards, in electric transitions (usually E1, E2 and E3). Some levels cannot be directly populated, such as those requiring M1 transitions. Populating higher spin states is increasingly hard, as it requires multi-step Coulomb excitation — the first excitation (e.g. from $0^+ \rightarrow 2^+$) requires a certain beam rate, but the second step (from $2^+ \rightarrow 4^+$) would require much more, so “a beam rate that is too low renders an experiment non-feasible” [29].

Despite the difficulties in performing such an experiment, CoulEx is the “tool of choice” [28] for probing shape coexistence. It can yield E2 matrix elements, which not only describe the strength of deformation (from the magnitude), but also the type of deformation, oblate or prolate (from the sign of the matrix element).

III.C. Detectors

Detectors fall into several broad categories, including semiconductor detectors (e.g. Ge(Li), HPGe and Si(Li)) and scintillation detectors (e.g. LaBr₃(Ce)).

III.C.1. Semiconductor: Ge(Li), HPGe and Si(Li)

In semiconducting detectors, the energy gap between the valence and conduction bands in the material is not quite as large as in insulators, but not as small as in conductors. Given enough excitation energy, electrons can ‘jump’ the gap, and form an electron-hole pair. When radiation passes through detectors, it can deposit energy in the semiconducting material and cause these excitations. The charge detected in the material from these electron-hole pairs can be used to find the energy of the incident radiation, and construct a spectrum.

Semiconductor detectors are known for their excellent energy resolution, but poor time resolution

Figure 9: Diagram of the fusion-evaporation process. The projectile (a) is fired at the target nucleus (A) and forms a compound nucleus (C^*). C^* then decays through light particle emission, forming a more stable residue, B. At any point after contact, the nucleus can also fission, forming fission daughters, F_1 and F_2 . Figure from Ref. [30].

(when the γ -ray was detected), and are therefore often used when knowing the energy of the incident radiation is most important.

Ge(Li) In the first half of the 20th Century, Ge crystals were already in use for γ -ray detection, but impurities were a limiting factor. It was discovered that, by doping Ge with a Li donor, these limitations could be greatly reduced, which “sparked tremendous progress” [31] in γ -ray spectroscopy in the late 1960’s, but order to maintain the correct chemical structure the detectors had to be cooled by liquid nitrogen (LN2) at all times. Improved resolution from Li was worth this impracticality, as resolution is vitally important in spectroscopy. These Li-drifted detectors – Ge(Li) – were crucial to nuclear structure development, and were the industry standard for two decades.

HPGe Ge(Li) detectors were eventually succeeded by High-purity Ge (HPGe) detectors in the 1980’s, as improved production mechanisms allowed for incredibly pure Ge crystals; some with impurities as low as $10^{-11}\%$. These detectors had the advantage that they could be stored at non-cryogenic temperatures without destroying any vital chemical structure (although they still require LN2 cooling during operation). They were also less susceptible to radiation damage, and they could be annealed (baked at high temperatures) to repair the damage they did receive [31]. Single crystals could be grown in shapes that maximised the ‘depletion volume’ (radiation detection volume), allowing for improved efficiency. Overall, the greater efficiency, resolution, and practicality of these detectors was a great technological leap, and lead to greatly improved experimental data.

Si(Li) Si(Li) – Li doped Si – detectors are also semiconductor detectors, but they differ from the Ge-based detectors mainly in the types of radiation that they tend to detect. Whereas Ge detectors are used for γ spectroscopy, Si(Li) detectors are best suited to electron spectroscopy. Si ($Z = 14$) is much lighter than Ge ($Z = 32$), and as such, γ radiation is less

likely to interact with it, allowing for an electron spectrum with improved peak-to-background ratio.

III.C.2. Scintillator: LaBr₃(Ce)

Scintillation detectors consist of a scintillating material coupled to a photomultiplier tube (PMT). The scintillating, luminescent material absorbs incident radiation and then emits a number of photons proportional to the energy of the incident radiation [32]. The PMT then absorbs these photons, and emits photoelectrons. The PMT uses anodes and dynodes to multiply the photoelectrons, creating a cascade and increasing the signal strength. These electrical signals are used to construct a spectrum.

LaBr₃(Ce) While semiconductor detectors such as Ge(Li)’s and HPGe’s have very good γ -ray energy resolution, they have poor time resolution. When time measurements are important, scintillation detectors such as LaBr₃(Ce) are more appropriate. LaBr₃(Ce) – Ce doped LaBr₃ – detectors can have resolutions of 100 ps [33], and as such are especially useful for half-life measurements of excited states.

III.D. Analysis techniques

III.D.1. Gamma ray spectroscopy

Gamma ray spectroscopy is a powerful tool for the analysis of nuclear structure. When a nucleus decays from an excited state to the ground state, it can emit two kinds of radiation without becoming a new isotope – electrons and photons. The energy of an emitted photon is equivalent to the energy difference between the initial state and the final state, which usually places them in the γ region. Using γ -ray detectors, the energy of the γ -rays can be found, and a spectrum can be constructed. By knowing the energy and intensity of the observed peaks in the spectra, conclusions can begin to be drawn about the energy level scheme of the isotope. A common technique that can be used during γ -ray spectroscopy analysis is to place multiple γ detectors in an array around the decaying nuclei, and keep track of the time that each γ -ray hit was registered. Coincident γ -rays –

Figure 10: A partial level scheme of ^{192}Hg . Note that the 422.8 keV transition is in coincidence with all three of the other transitions, but 786.3 keV and 745.5 keV are parallel, and therefore will not be found in coincidence with each other. Data taken from ENSDF, Ref. [14].

detected within a narrow time window, comparable to the timing resolution of the detector – were likely emitted by the same decaying nucleus. Those that are not in coincidence are not present in the same cascade of decays, and may be parallel (see Fig 10) or products of different parent isomers. By finding which γ -rays are in coincidence and which ones are not, different possible cascade paths can be found and a level scheme can be verifiably constructed.

III.D.2. Gamma-gamma fast timing technique

Although Coulomb excitation is the best way to find E2 matrix elements [28], when it comes to lifetime measurements, there are many experimental techniques that can be applied. From lifetime measurements, the reduced quadrupole transition probability $B(E2)$ can be determined, which can indicate the magnitude of deformation, but *cannot* distinguish between oblate or prolate. One such technique, suited to timespans in the nanosecond to picosecond range [34] is γ - γ fast-timing spectroscopy.

Such experiments measure the time between the detection of a γ -ray that decays *in* to a level and the γ -ray that decays *out* of it, to see how long the nucleus remained in the intermediate state for. While the need for an accurate timing measurement is unquestionable in this type of experiment, a precise knowledge of the energy of detected γ -rays is also important, so it is common practice to use a hybrid array of semiconductor and scintillation detectors. As nuclear decay spectra can have many peaks, the ability to precisely gate on a particular γ -ray and only see its coincidences can make the spectra much clearer. To take a lifetime measurement of, for example, the 2_1^+ state in Fig. 10, first the strongest three- γ decay cascade through that level would be identified (e.g. $6_1^+ \rightarrow 4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$). The γ -ray that does not directly transition to/from the state of interest ($6_1^+ \rightarrow 4_1^+$; 745.5 keV) would be found in the semiconductor spectrum and gated upon, so that only coincident γ -rays are seen in the scintillator spectra. The other two γ -rays, the ones into ($4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$; 634.8 keV) and out of ($2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$; 422.8 keV) the level would be located in the scintillation spectra, and the time be-

tween the two detections could be found. This allows for “unambiguous selectivity ... of a specific level ... without the contribution of other levels” [12].

IV. PREVIOUS WORKS

IV.A. Level schemes of low-lying states

A comprehensive level scheme is the solid ground upon which other knowledge is built; without knowing energy levels, spin-parity assignments and transitions, it is difficult to perform other experiments (which tend to rely on this information) to measure lifetimes or calculate quadrupole deformation parameters. For ^{192}Hg , there are three main studies that have contributed to the low-lying energy level scheme, discussed below. All of these studies are γ spectroscopy experiments which populate the excited ^{192}Hg levels by the beam implantation and subsequent EC decay of ^{192}Tl .

IV.A.1. Petry

Our initial understanding of ^{192}Hg 's energy level structure is built upon Petry *et al.*'s 1968 study of four even-even Hg isotopes, $^{192-198}\text{Hg}$ [35]. They used a form of beam implantation (into aluminium foil, rather than Mylar) to perform a γ -ray spectroscopy analysis of Hg. Their array included three Ge(Li) γ detectors (3.0 - 5.9 keV resolution at 1.33 MeV), and two Si(Li) electron detectors (3.7 keV & 6 keV resolution at 400 keV). An example of their spectra can be seen in Fig. 11.

Using coincidence data from this equipment, nine of the most intense γ -rays in the $A = 192$ spectra were identified, of which eight were placed in an energy level scheme, shown in Fig. 12 which is successfully reproduced by future experiments. There is frequent reference to a “four-component cascade” (which for this isotope, is the $133\text{ keV} \rightarrow 786\text{ keV} \rightarrow 635\text{ keV} \rightarrow 423\text{ keV}$ decay path) that is common to the level schemes of $^{192-198}\text{Hg}$. While this cascade is firmly established for the other three isotopes in the study, the coincidence data does not provide enough

information to say this of ^{192}Hg . They instead place the members of the cascade by following the systematic trend of the neighbouring isotopes. This reveals a deficiency in the data collected, but despite this, the work done by Petry *et al.* laid strong foundations for future experiments to improve upon.

IV.A.2. Vandlik

Building on this, Vandlik *et al.* (1975) [36] performed a study of $^{190,192}\text{Hg}$ using one Ge(Li) γ detector (3.7 keV resolution at 422 keV) and one Si(Li) electron detector (4.4 keV resolution at 339 keV). No spectra are provided in the paper.

Through this study, 49 γ -rays were identified in the spectrum of ^{192}Hg , of which 40 were previously unobserved. They confirm Petry *et al.*'s arrangement of γ -rays, and are able to place 11 additional γ -rays in the scheme. This level scheme (Fig. 13) is proposed on the basis of similar structures in the neighbouring Hg isotopes.

IV.A.3. Sousa

Sousa *et al.*'s 1981 [37] experiment was performed at Oak Ridge, using Ge(Li) γ detectors (with typical resolutions of 2.1 keV at 1332 keV), and Si(Li) electron detectors (2.3 keV resolution at 1064 keV). The number of detectors used is absent from the paper, but they must have multiple detectors, as they perform coincidence analysis. The technological advantage in this experiment compared to Vandlik *et al.* is made clear in the greatly improved resolution ($>3\text{ keV}$ to 2.1 keV) at much higher energies ($\sim 400\text{ keV}$ to 1332 keV), as well as having multiple Ge(Li) detectors. Their spectrum (Fig. 15) has much greater statistics than Petry *et al.*'s spectrum (Ref. 11), shown in the order-of-magnitude increase in the number of counts in the 423 keV peak.

With this improved equipment, Sousa *et al.* catalogued 74 γ -rays in the ^{192}Hg spectrum, 25 more than was previously known. Of those 74 γ -rays, they were able to place 31 in a level scheme, of which 14 agree with Vandlik *et al.* - Fig. 14. What was previously 10 levels expanded to 22, and each γ placement is supported by γ - γ coincidence data. They discuss

Figure 11: Example of Petry *et al.*'s ^{192}Hg spectra. Top: Full spectrum. Bottom: Coincidence with 423.0 keV γ -ray. Note that the top of the 423 keV peak is approx. 10,000 counts per channel. Partial figure from Ref. [35].

Figure 12: Petry *et al.*'s proposed level scheme. Transitions that originate from circles have been confirmed by γ - γ coincidence spectroscopy, which in this case, is all of them. Figure from Ref. [35].

the possible spin-parity assignments (1^+ , 2^+ , 3^+) of the new 1535.5 keV level they place, and argue a 3^+ assignment based on the lack of observed transition from the 1535.5 keV level to the ground state.

IV.A.4. Comparison

The most striking comparison that can be made between these studies is the use of γ - γ coincidence analysis. While Petry *et al.* and Sousa *et al.* use multiple Ge(Li) detectors and get coincidence data from them, Vandlik *et al.* do not. By only using one Ge(Li) detector, there is no opportunity for γ - γ coincidence analysis, which is a significant limiting factor of Vandlik *et al.*'s study. Without coincidence information, energy levels and transitions are instead placed through comparison to the structure of neighbouring isotopes and isotones. This argument relies heavily on the assumption that the nuclear structure will follow a smooth, predictable trend as A and Z change. By not collecting coincidence data, they remove the possibility of a null result. Although Petry *et al.* also use neighbouring isotopes to guide their level scheme, they *do* have coincidence data, and are therefore able to *disprove* their assumptions. Vandlik's study doesn't have this ability and – perhaps

Figure 13: Vandlik *et al.*'s proposed level scheme. Wider arrows indicate higher intensity γ -rays. The proposed energies, intensities and electromagnetic transitions (e.g. M1, E2) are shown. Parent isomers are shown populating certain states. Figure from Ref. [36].

as a result of this – there are disagreements between this study and the later study by Sousa *et al.*.

The major disagreement between Vandlik *et al.* and Sousa *et al.* is regarding the first 3^+ state; while Vandlik *et al.* place the level at 1592.9 keV, Sousa *et al.* place it at 1535.5 keV. Vandlik *et al.* seem to propose the level based on the observance of γ -rays at 535.4 keV and 478.8 keV. They also place a weak depopulating 1110 keV γ -ray from that level to the first 2^+ , which is unusual as they do not list

this γ -ray as one that they observed, and therefore could have been placed by analogy to neighbouring nuclei. In contrast to this, Sousa *et al.* propose an energy level at 1535.5 keV because, through γ - γ coincidence analysis, they found the $4^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ 1113.0 keV γ -ray to be a doublet. They place the second component of this doublet at $3^+ (1535.5) \rightarrow 2^+ (422.8)$, and their argument for such a placement is supported by coincidence analysis. Further dividing the two, Vandlik places a 478.8 keV γ -ray populat-

Figure 14: Sousa *et al.*'s proposed level scheme. Transition arrows with dots on the tip indicate that they have been confirmed through γ - γ coincidence. Some proposed electromagnetic transitions (e.g. M1, E2) are shown. Figure from Ref. [37].

ing the (2_2^+), whereas Sousa found coincidence data suggesting that a similar 477.6 keV γ -ray populates the 4_1^+ . Both originate from the disputed level, but Sousa's is more firmly evidenced. Vandlik *et al.*'s differing energy level is likely a result of their somewhat flawed methodology.

It should be noted that much of the rest of the Vandlik *et al.* level scheme is in agreement with Sousa *et al.*; the assumptions made were *often* correct, but are easily discounted when faced with contradicting evidence. Sousa *et al.*'s findings are more robust and rigorous and, as such, the current Evaluated Nuclear Structure Data File (ENSDF) level scheme for ^{192}Hg (^{192}Tl EC decay) is based almost entirely on Sousa

et al.'s findings.

The current ENSDF level scheme for the low-lying states of ^{192}Hg accessible by EC decay is quite sparse, and has not been improved upon since Sousa *et al.*'s 1981 study. While the ground state band has been identified (and confirmed through other experimental methods), every spin and parity assignment outside of the ground state band is tentative. There is also no excited 0^+ state identified. While Sousa's study was a comprehensive and well-argued paper, and very enlightening at the time, there is much room for improvement upon this level structure with modern HPGe detector arrays.

Figure 15: Example of Sousa *et al.*'s ^{192}Hg spectra, displayed as three sections for clarity. Peaks are labelled by their energy, and their source if they originate from anything other than a ^{192}Hg de-excitation. Note that the top of the 423 keV peak is approx. 100,000 counts per channel. Figure from Ref. [37].

IV.B. Transition strengths of low-lying states

Measuring the transition strengths of certain transitions in nuclei can be very enlightening as to the shape deformation of those states. True E2 transition strengths are difficult to measure, and are usually found through CoulEx experiments. Reduced E2 transition strengths – $B(E2)$'s – are easier to calculate, and can be found by measuring the lifetime of the initial state. These lifetime-based methods are employed by Esmaylzadeh *et al.* and Olaizola *et al.* to analyse ^{192}Hg . An example of a CoulEx experiment in the Hg isotopic chain is also briefly evaluated.

IV.B.1. Esmaylzadeh

Esmaylzadeh *et al.*'s study used fusion-evaporation techniques (Section III.B.2.) to populate states in even-even $^{190-196}\text{Hg}$. They utilized the HORUS facilities at the University of Cologne, which included 8 HPGe detectors and 9 LaBr₃(Ce) detectors, of which six had Compton-suppressing shielding.

Esmaylzadeh *et al.*'s paper presents data on the lifetimes and $B(E2)$ values of 2_1^+ and 4_1^+ states in $^{190,192,194,196}\text{Hg}$, and an additional, negative parity state in $^{192,194,196}\text{Hg}$. The summary of their results, and comparison with Olaizola's results, can be seen in Table 1. The motivation of this study was to “complete the systematics” of experimental $B(E2)$ values for $2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ and $4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$ from ^{180}Hg to ^{204}Hg , as $^{190-196}\text{Hg}$ were lacking.

IV.B.2. Olaizola

The more recent study by Olaizola *et al.* was performed using the GRIFFIN array at TRIUMF, using 15 HPGe-clover detectors and 7 LaBr₃(Ce) crystals. Olaizola *et al.* use the EC decay of Tl to Hg to study even-even $^{188-200}\text{Hg}$ isotopes. Data taken in this same experiment is analysed in the thesis that this review intends to contextualize.

Olaizola *et al.*'s paper presents confirmational data for all but one of the lifetimes shown in Esmaylzadeh *et al.*'s results, and adds eight more in the $^{190,192,194,196}\text{Hg}$ isotopes. As this study is slightly

wider in scope, there is also data presented for $^{188,198,200}\text{Hg}$. The summary of Olaizola *et al.*'s $B(E2)$ values, with comparison, can be found in Table 1.

IV.B.3. Comparison

Esmaylzadeh *et al.* compare their results to the two theoretical models of this nucleus discussed in Section II.A.. They conclude that they have closer agreement with the IBM-CM model “by taking the surrounding isotopes into account” [11], not through their own results. Upon closer inspection of Fig. 16, the data that was taken in this study (marked by stars) doesn't seem to convincingly rule out either option. The error bars are large enough to include predictions from both models for $^{190,192,196}\text{Hg}$. Even worse, the ^{194}Hg data points contradict – IBM-CM is excluded in the $2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ transition, but IBM-2 is excluded in the $4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$ transition.

The favourable population of high-spin yrast states in fusion evaporation experiments is partly the cause for these large errors. In some of the isotopes, key transitions have doublet transitions at higher spin states. For example, in ^{190}Hg , the $2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ transition has an energy of 416.4 keV, but the $14_1^+ \rightarrow 12_1^+$ transition has an energy of 419.9 keV. LaBr₃(Ce) detectors have an energy resolution of 3-4%, which is too large to resolve peaks such as these. Most relevant to this review, the $2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ and $4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$ transitions of ^{192}Hg are both contaminated (by $14_1^+ \rightarrow 12_1^+$ and $8_1^+ \rightarrow 6_1^+$ respectively). The magnitude of this problem can be seen in Fig. 17. Esmaylzadeh *et al.* argue that this contamination can be accounted for by increasing the error margin by 4 ps – they arrive at this value by “assuming that the lifetime of [the contaminating states] is shorter than 5 ps”. While there was little option other than to base their error inflation on this assumption, the work becomes unfortunately weaker as a result.

As can be seen in Table 1, for areas where the Esmaylzadeh *et al.* and Olaizola *et al.* data sets overlap, there is good agreement. The $B(E2)$ values found in Olaizola *et al.* are within the error proposed by Esmaylzadeh *et al.*, implying that their assumptions when inflating the error were reasonable. They are also both in agreement with the few known val-

Figure 16: Graph of Esmaylzadeh *et al.*'s experimental B(E2) values for the (a) $2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ (b) and $4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$ transitions, marked with red stars. Existing experimental values are shown as red circles. Theoretical comparisons are made to IBM-CM [15] (green circles) and IBM-2 [2] (blue circles) calculations. Figure from Ref. [11].

Figure 17: Example of Esmaylzadeh *et al.*'s HPGe (blue) and LaBr (red) singles spectra for ^{192}Hg . The relevant transitions to determine the lifetimes of the 2_1^+ and 4_1^+ are marked, as are any major contaminating peaks. Peaks resulting from other isotopes are marked with "C". Partial figure from Ref. [11].

ues quoted in the Nuclear Data Sheets [38]. This is encouraging, and supports the validity of the fast-

timing methods used and quality of the results produced.

The errors in Olaizola *et al.*'s study are, in almost all cases, significantly smaller. Olaizola *et al.*, using EC decay, do not populate the high-spin 'problem' states, and as such, do not suffer from doublet peaks as much. This improved accuracy is most important for the $2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ transitions (Table 1) where, for example, the error of the B(E2) value of the ^{192}Hg , $2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ transition is reduced from 42^{+26}_{-12} to $51(4)$. More accurate experimental data allows for more "meaningful comparison" to theoretical predictions which, as shown in Figs. 18a and 18b, shows a much more definitive exclusion of the IBM-2 predictions, and a much closer agreement with IBM-CM. This work supports the predictions that shape coexistence occurs "up to ^{188}Hg , with maybe a weak effect in ^{190}Hg " [12], and then doesn't occur from ^{192}Hg onwards.

Figure 18: Olaizola *et al.*'s $B(E2)$ values of the (a) $2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ and (b) $4_1^+ \rightarrow 2_1^+$ transitions (red stars), compared to literature and theory. Literature values (blue squares) are taken from Esmaylzadeh *et al.* [11] for $^{190-194}\text{Hg}$, and Ref. [38] for all others. IBM-CM from Ref. [15]. IBM-2 from Ref. [2].

Figures from Ref. [12].

IV.B.4. Coulomb excitation; an alternative technique

Moving beyond ^{192}Hg specifically, a recent CoulEx study of Hg isotopes in the shape coexisting region $^{182-188}\text{Hg}$ has been performed by Bree *et al* at REX-ISOLDE. CoulEx studies are especially valuable, as they can directly measure E2 transition strengths, which the other, lifetime-based methods cannot do. This paper presented evidence that the Hg ground states are “weakly deformed ... consistent with an oblate-like deformation”, and the excited 0^+ states were more deformed. They conclude that their data implies “significant changes in the composition of the 2_1^+ states” as you move to lighter isotopes. This valuable study compared their results to theoretical predictions, and pointed to discrepancies as a sign of “missing ingredients in the calculations”, and acknowledge that the differences are “not understood”. The authors also compare and collaborate with other experimentalists, drawing in “data from beta-decay [electron capture] studies of $^{182,184}\text{Tl}$ ” - the same type of experiment that this review intends to accompany. The work shown here is valuable and well-argued,

and again demonstrates the importance of using diverse experimental techniques to advance the field of nuclear structure.

V. SUMMARY

There are, at present, two theoretical studies that have tackled ^{192}Hg - the IBM-2 study by Nomura *et al.* [2], and the later IBM-CM study by García-Ramos & Heyde [15]. The IBM-CM calculations can more accurately predict experimental observations, but the calculations incorporate experimental data to constrain parameters. This makes the model very dependant on the accuracy and reliability of the experimental data, and causes notable weakness in areas where no experimental data is available. Despite this, the observed trends and shape structures are well reproduced, and the calculated values for lifetime and reduced transition probabilities closely predict recent measurements [12]. Nomura *et al.*'s IBM-2 calculations are often less accurate than García-Ramos & Heyde's IBM-CM counterpart, but they have the advantage of being self-contained and independent of

experimental values. These calculations suffered from a simplistic mathematical model and a high sensitivity to the energy density function (EDF) chosen to restrain the variables. The trends of low-lying yrast states are well reproduced, but high-spin or non-yrast states are less accurate, and do not follow the experimental trends. There are several types of EDF, and they are often being improved and expanded, so a revision of these calculations – with a larger model space, improved EDF and more complex interactions – may improve its predictions greatly. IBM-CM calculations would also benefit from a revision, with improved and expanded experimental data. Overall, IBM-CM has a much greater predictive power than IBM-2, and can be more reliably used to direct future experimental studies.

The recent MCSM investigation of $^{177-186}\text{Hg}$ produced some very promising results, and even presented arguments for which specific proton and neutron orbitals were driving shape coexistence and shape deformation in the nuclei. Such complex models are becoming more viable with the continuous improvements in theoretical techniques and available computational power. These methods represent an exciting future for nuclear structure physics.

There are many alternative approaches to the analysis of nuclear structure, each of which can provide different types of data and must be taken together to provide a full description of the nucleus. There are also many methods of populating excited states in nuclei, which can each access different states in the nucleus; some (such as fusion evaporation) are more suited to populating high-spin states, whereas others (such as electron capture decay) can more easily populate non-yrast states. Ease, intensity and contamination can also vary greatly between methods. No single experiment can determine everything about an isotope, and indeed should not attempt to. The use of diverse experimental methods is important, as comparisons of data from different kinds of analysis can lead to the discovery of new physics.

The primary focus of this review is the present knowledge of low-lying, low-spin energy levels of ^{192}Hg , obtained through EC decay of ^{192}Tl . There are only three published studies of this type, performed between 1968 and 1981. Petry *et al.* is the

first study to establish the energies and coincidences of the most intense γ -rays in the decay of this isotope. The energy level diagram proposed has been corroborated by future studies, but is quite limited – there are only 7 levels and 8 transitions shown. Vandlik *et al.* attempt to update and expand the level scheme, but their study only used one Ge(Li) γ -ray detector, so they were unable to identify coincidences. Their study identified many more previously unobserved γ -rays – 40 more, in fact – but arrives at a level scheme through comparison to neighbouring isotopes, not through coincidence analysis. This is a somewhat weak way to construct a level scheme, susceptible to inaccuracies due to unpredicted changes in nuclear structure or false placements propagating from neighbour to neighbour. A more compelling level scheme is presented by Sousa *et al.*, who use coincidence analysis techniques and higher-resolution detectors to perform their study. Sousa *et al.* expand the number of known γ -rays to 74, and manage to assign 31 of these to transitions in a 22-state level scheme. They identify the low-lying ~ 1113 keV peak found by both Petry *et al.* and Vandlik *et al.* to be a doublet, and their argument for the placement of each transition in the doublet is convincing. This previously unidentified doublet is argued to originate from the 3_1^+ state, which is at disagreement with Vandlik *et al.*'s earlier study. The evidence supporting Sousa *et al.*'s argument is far more comprehensive than Vandlik *et al.*'s, which inspires confidence in the validity of their level scheme. As a result, the current ENSDF sheet for ^{192}Hg (through EC decay of ^{192}Tl) is based almost solely on Sousa's findings.

Despite this, the present knowledge of ^{192}Hg 's low-lying structure is in many ways incomplete, and can be greatly improved upon (see Fig. 5). No 0_2^+ state has been identified — the only even-even isotope from ^{180}Hg to ^{204}Hg for which this is true. Every spin-parity assignment outside of the ground state band is tentative, often with multiple options presented. There is much that could be gained from a modern investigation of the isotope, as there have been many technological advancements since the last γ spectroscopy study in 1981, almost 40 years ago. Modern facilities can produce beam with far fewer contaminants, which would reduce the background

in the spectra, and access to large arrays of modern HPGe detectors – which have excellent energy resolution and are superior to the older Ge(Li) detectors – could produce high-statistic spectra with clearer, more easily resolved peaks. Such advancements could enable the location of the 0_2^+ state, and the firm identification of many more.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Deformed nuclear shapes are of great interest to nuclear structure physicists, as they are the result of complex interactions within the nucleus that have remained nebulous for decades. A particularly interesting manifestation of these nuclear forces is the phenomenon of shape coexistence, in which two or more bands of states are found to lie at similar energies, but exhibit different shapes and, as such, behave quite differently. Shape coexistence is found to occur across the nuclear chart, but the region around the magic number $Z = 82$ has been especially enlightening to study, as it seems especially susceptible to shape coexistence. The first excited 0^+ state (0_2^+) is especially important in the identification of shape coexistence, as it is the bandhead for the secondary structure of intruding deformed states.

The current literature regarding the low-lying, low-spin energy levels of ^{192}Hg ($Z = 80$) is almost 40 years old, and – while enlightening when it was published – fails to establish many key points of interest, such as locating the 0_2^+ state, or providing confident spin-parity assignments outside of the ground state band. This is critical, as other experimental techniques (such as γ - γ fast timing and CoulEx, which can determine shape deformation) rely upon this information. The collaborative nature of experimental and theoretical nuclear physics – which has thus far been crucial to the advancement of the field as a whole – also makes it especially important to identify and remove such weaknesses. As such, the need for a modern analysis of ^{192}Hg is established.

This literature review is written with the intent of providing context for an upcoming thesis on the γ -ray spectroscopy analysis of ^{192}Hg , performed using the GRIFFIN array at TRIUMF, Canada. Modern

experimental and analytical techniques (such as γ - γ angular correlation, which can firmly establish spin-parity assignments, but has not yet been applied to ^{192}Hg) will be employed, with the intent of strengthening the stated weaknesses in data regarding ^{192}Hg . Such experiments can, by improving our available *experimental* data, strengthen our understanding of the nucleus *on the whole*.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I wish to thank my supervisors and colleagues – A.B. Garnsworthy, B. Olaizola, and S. Gillespie – for their guidance and support in the research and writing of this review. TRIUMF receives funding through a contribution agreement through the National Research Council Canada.

Nucleus	J_i^π	J_f^π	Esmay. B(E2) [W.u.]	Olaiz. B(E2) [W.u.]	Nucl. Tables B(E2) [W.u.]
^{188}Hg	2_1^+	0_1^+	-	50(11)	53.8(84)
	2_2^+	2_1^+	-	> 8	-
	2_2^+	0_1^+	-	> 1	-
	4_1^+	2_1^+	-	> 4	-
	4_2^+	4_1^+	-	> 33	-
	4_2^+	2_2^+	-	> 26	-
	4_2^+	2_1^+	-	> 0.32	-
	6_1^+	(4_1^+)	-	> 110	-
	6_1^+	4_2^+	-	> 250	-
	6_1^+	4_1^+	-	> 90	-
	6_2^+	4_2^+	-	> 1.1	-
6_1^+	4_1^+	-	> 0.8	-	
^{190}Hg	2_1^+	0_1^+	46_{-14}^{+35}	45(3)	-
	4_1^+	2_1^+	> 10.8	18(14)	-
	6_1^+	4_1^+	-	6(3)	-
	7_1^-	5_1^-	-	> 30	-
^{192}Hg	2_1^+	0_1^+	42_{-12}^{+26}	51(4)	-
	4_1^+	2_1^+	20_{-9}^{+99}	21(15)	-
	6_1^+	4_1^+	-	0.51(7)	-
	7_1^-	5_1^-	-	37(2)	-
^{194}Hg	2_1^+	0_1^+	39_{-6}^{+9}	30(2)	-
	4_1^+	2_1^+	17_{-6}^{+22}	> 27	-
	7_1^-	5_1^-	-	34.4(3)	-
	9_1^-	7_1^-	33_{-1}^{+1}	-	-
^{196}Hg	2_1^+	0_1^+	36_{-4}^{+5}	36(7)	33.8(24)
	4_1^+	2_1^+	19_{-8}^{+39}	20(15)	-
	7_1^-	5_1^-	-	33(1)	-
^{198}Hg	2_1^+	0_1^+	-	28(4)	28.05(20)
	4_1^+	2_1^+	-	> 16	-
	7_1^-	5_1^-	-	29.5(5)	-
^{200}Hg	2_1^+	0_1^+	-	26(2)	24.6(81)
	4_1^+	2_1^+	-	20(9)	-
	0_2^+	2_1^+	-	8(4)	-
	2_2^+	0_2^+	-	4(3)	-
	2_2^+	4_1^+	-	0.6(5)	-
	2_2^+	2_1^+	-	1.0(8)	-
	2_2^+	0_1^+	-	0.10(8)	-

Table 1: Comparison table of experimental B(E2) values for even-even $^{188-200}\text{Hg}$ from Esmaylzadeh *et al.* [11], Olaizola *et al.* [12], and the pre-existing literature [38]. J_i^π and J_f^π are the spin-parity assignment of the initial and final states of the transition, respectively. B(E2) values are given in Weisskopf units (W.u.).

References

- [1] K. Heyde and J.L. Wood. “Shape coexistence in atomic nuclei”. In: *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 83 (4 Nov. 2011), pp. 1467–1521. DOI: 10.1103/RevModPhys.83.1467. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/RevModPhys.83.1467>.
- [2] K. Nomura, R. Rodríguez-Guzmán, and L.M. Robledo. “Shape evolution and the role of intruder configurations in Hg isotopes within the interacting boson model based on a Gogny energy density functional”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 87 (6 June 2013), p. 064313. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.87.064313. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.87.064313>.
- [3] Bing-Nan, L. et al. “Potential energy surfaces of actinide and transfermium nuclei from multi-dimensional constraint covariant density functional theories”. In: *EPJ Web of Conferences* 38 (2012), p. 05003. DOI: 10.1051/epjconf/20123805003. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/20123805003>.
- [4] T. Otsuka and Y. Tsunoda. “The role of shell evolution in shape coexistence”. In: *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* 43.2 (Jan. 2016), p. 024009. DOI: 10.1088/0954-3899/43/2/024009. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1088/0954-3899/43/2/024009>.
- [5] T. Otsuka et al. “Evolution of nuclear structure in exotic nuclei driven by nuclear forces”. In: (2018). arXiv: 1805.06501 [nucl-th].
- [6] A.N. Andreyev et al. “A triplet of differently shaped spin-zero states in the atomic nucleus ^{186}Pb ”. In: *Nature* 405 (May 2000), 430 EP -. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1038/35013012>.
- [7] A Poves. “Shape coexistence in nuclei”. In: *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* 43.2 (Jan. 2016), p. 020401. DOI: 10.1088/0954-3899/43/2/020401. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1088/0954-3899/43/2/020401>.
- [8] K. Matsuyanagi et al. “Microscopic derivation of the quadrupole collective Hamiltonian for shape coexistence/mixing dynamics”. In: *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* 43.2 (Jan. 2016), p. 024006. DOI: 10.1088/0954-3899/43/2/024006. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1088/0954-3899/43/2/024006>.
- [9] N. Bree et al. “Shape Coexistence in the Neutron-Deficient Even-Even $^{182-188}\text{Hg}$ Isotopes Studied via Coulomb Excitation”. In: *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 112 (16 Apr. 2014), p. 162701. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.112.162701. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.112.162701>.
- [10] L. P. Gaffney et al. “Shape coexistence in neutron-deficient Hg isotopes studied via lifetime measurements in $^{184,186}\text{Hg}$ and two-state mixing calculations”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 89 (2 Feb. 2014), p. 024307. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.89.024307. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.89.024307>.
- [11] A. Esmaylzadeh et al. “Lifetime determination in Hg 190 , 192 , 194 , 196 via fast-timing spectroscopy”. In: *Physical Review C* 98 (July 2018). DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.98.014313.
- [12] B. Olaizola et al. “Shape coexistence in the neutron-deficient lead region: A systematic study of lifetimes in the even-even $^{188-200}\text{Hg}$ with GRIFFIN”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* ((in press)).
- [13] M. O. Kortelahti et al. “Shape coexistence in ^{190}Hg ”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 43 (2 Feb. 1991), pp. 484–488. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.43.484. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.43.484>.

- [14] Coral M. Baglin. “Nuclear Data Sheets for $A = 192$ ”. In: *Nuclear Data Sheets* 113.8 (2012), pp. 1871–2111. ISSN: 0090-3752. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nds.2012.08.001>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0090375212000579>.
- [15] J.E. Garcia-Ramos and K. Heyde. “Nuclear shape coexistence: A study of the even-even Hg isotopes using the interacting boson model with configuration mixing”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 89 (1 Jan. 2014), p. 014306. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.89.014306. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.89.014306>.
- [16] B.A. Marsh et al. “Characterization of the shape-staggering effect in mercury nuclei”. In: *Nature Physics* 14.12 (2018), pp. 1163–1167. ISSN: 1745-2481. DOI: 10.1038/s41567-018-0292-8. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41567-018-0292-8>.
- [17] Walter Pfeifer. “An Introduction to the Interacting Boson Model of the Atomic Nucleus, Part I”. In: (Oct. 2002).
- [18] L M Robledo, T R Rodriguez, and R R Rodriguez-Guzmán. “Mean field and beyond description of nuclear structure with the Gogny force: a review”. In: *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* 46.1 (Dec. 2018), p. 013001. DOI: 10.1088/1361-6471/aadebd. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6471/aadebd>.
- [19] C. Müller-Gatermann et al. “Shape coexistence in ^{178}Hg ”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 99 (5 May 2019), p. 054325. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.99.054325. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.99.054325>.
- [20] F. James and M. Roos. “Minuit - a system for function minimization and analysis of the parameter errors and correlations”. In: *Computer Physics Communications* 10.6 (1975), pp. 343–367. ISSN: 0010-4655. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-4655\(75\)90039-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-4655(75)90039-9). URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0010465575900399>.
- [21] Otsuka T. “Monte Carlo shell model”. In: *Nuclear Physics A* 693.1 (2001). Radioactive Nuclear Beams, pp. 383–393. ISSN: 0375-9474. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0375-9474\(00\)00605-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0375-9474(00)00605-9). URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0375947400006059>.
- [22] S. Sels et al. “Shape staggering of midshell mercury isotopes from in-source laser spectroscopy compared with density-functional-theory and Monte Carlo shell-model calculations”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 99 (4 Apr. 2019), p. 044306. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.99.044306. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.99.044306>.
- [23] P.J. Bryant. “A Brief history and review of accelerators”. In: *CAS-CERN Accelerator School: 5th general accelerator physics course, Jyväskylä, Finland, 7-18 Sep 1992: Proceedings. 2 vol.* 1992, pp. 1–16.
- [24] K. Sasa et al. “Construction of the 6 MV Tandem Accelerator System for Various Ion Beam Applications at the University of Tsukuba”. In: *Proceedings, 13th Heavy Ion Accelerator Technology Conference (HIAT2015): Yokohama, Japan, September 7-11, 2015.* 2016, THM2C02. DOI: 10.18429/JACoW-HIAT2015-THM2C02.
- [25] D.A. Bromley. *Treatise on Heavy-Ion Science: Volume 8: Nuclei Far From Stability.* Springer US, 2012. ISBN: 9781461307136. URL: <https://books.google.ca/books?id=M4f1BwAAQBAJ>.
- [26] Y. Blumenfeld, T. Nilsson, and P. Van Duppen. “Facilities and methods for radioactive ion beam production”. In: *Physica Scripta* T152 (Jan. 2013), p. 014023. DOI: 10.1088/0031-8949/2013/t152/014023. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1088/0031-8949/2013/t152/014023>.

- [27] O. Klein and Y. Nishina. “Über die Streuung von Strahlung durch freie Elektronen nach der neuen relativistischen Quantendynamik von Dirac”. In: *Zeitschrift für Physik* 52.11 (Nov. 1929), pp. 853–868. ISSN: 0044-3328. DOI: 10.1007/BF01366453. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01366453>.
- [28] A. Görgen and W. Korten. “Coulomb excitation studies of shape coexistence in atomic nuclei”. In: *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* 43.2 (Jan. 2016), p. 024002. DOI: 10.1088/0954-3899/43/2/024002. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1088/0954-3899/43/2/024002>.
- [29] T. Glasmacher. “Testing the Structure of Exotic Nuclei via Coulomb Excitation of Radioactive Ion Beams at Intermediate Energies”. In: *The Euroscool Lectures on Physics with Exotic Beams, Vol. III*. Ed. by J.S. Al-Khalili and E. Roeckl. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2009, pp. 27–55. ISBN: 978-3-540-85839-3. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-540-85839-3_2. URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-85839-3_2.
- [30] Greg Henning. “Stability of Transfermium Elements at High Spin: Measuring the Fission Barrier of 254 No”. In: (Sept. 2012).
- [31] J. Eberth and J. Simpson. “From Ge(Li) detectors to gamma-ray tracking arrays—50 years of gamma spectroscopy with germanium detectors”. In: *Progress in Particle and Nuclear Physics* 60.2 (2008), pp. 283–337. ISSN: 0146-6410. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnpnp.2007.09.001>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0146641007000828>.
- [32] Utz Kramar. “X-ray Fluorescence Spectrometers”. In: *Encyclopedia of Spectroscopy and Spectrometry*. Ed. by J.C. Lindon. Oxford: Elsevier, 1999, pp. 2467–2477. ISBN: 978-0-12-226680-5. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1006/rwsp.2000.0336>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B0122266803003367>.
- [33] A. Oberstedt, R. Billnert, and S. Oberstedt. “Gamma-ray Measurements with LaBr₃: Ce Detectors -thinking Outside the Box”. In: *Physics Procedia* 31 (2012). GAMMA-1 Emission of Prompt Gamma-Rays in Fission and Related Topics, pp. 21–28. ISSN: 1875-3892. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phpro.2012.04.004>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S187538921201190X>.
- [34] L.M. Fraile. “Fast-timing spectroscopy at ISOLDE”. In: *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* 44.9 (Aug. 2017), p. 094004. DOI: 10.1088/1361-6471/aa8217. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6471/aa8217>.
- [35] R.F. Petry, R.A. Naumann, and J.S. Evans. “Levels in Even-Even Hg¹⁹², Hg¹⁹⁴, Hg¹⁹⁶, and Hg¹⁹⁸”. In: *Phys. Rev.* 174 (4 Oct. 1968), pp. 1441–1454. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRev.174.1441. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRev.174.1441>.
- [36] T.B. Vandlik et al. “Decay of the isotopes ¹⁹²Tl and ¹⁹⁰Tl”. In: *Yad. Fiz.* 22 (5 Nov. 1975), pp. 873–885.
- [37] D.C. Sousa et al. “Radioactive decay of mass-separated ¹⁹²Tl and ¹⁹²Pb”. In: *Phys. Rev. C* 24 (5 Nov. 1981), pp. 2245–2259. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevC.24.2245. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevC.24.2245>.
- [38] B. Pritychenko et al. “Tables of E2 transition probabilities from the first 2+ states in even-even nuclei”. In: *Atomic Data and Nuclear Data Tables* 107 (2016), pp. 1–139. ISSN: 0092-640X. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adt.2015.10.001>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0092640X15000406>.

Appendix B

Using χ^2 analysis techniques

A detailed examination of χ^2 and its statistical applications can be found at Ref. [41]. In brief, χ^2 is a measure of goodness-of-fit, i.e. the difference between the experimental data ('observation') and the fit applied to it ('expectation').

The original equation was proposed by Pearson in 1900 [42] and later modified by Neyman in 1949 [43] to take the form we most often see now, i.e.

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

where O is the observed result, and E is the expectation. This formula expresses total difference between data and fit for each data point, and so it increases for each new data point included. Essentially, the greater the value of i , the larger χ^2 will be.

The need to scale this value (making the meaning of χ^2 more widely

applicable) popularized the use of a *reduced* χ^2 value,

$$\frac{\chi^2}{NDF} = \frac{\sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}}{\# \text{ degrees of freedom}}$$

This reduced χ^2 value (χ^2/NDF) can be used to quantify and compare the quality of any fit, regardless of the number of data points. A χ^2/NDF of 1 indicates a perfect fit to the data, and $\chi^2/NDF \gg 1$ suggests that the fit is very poor, and does not accurately reproduce the underlying physical causes. Additionally, if $\chi^2/NDF < 1$, then the experimental data is being “over-fit”. Over-fitting suggests that the theoretical model has too much freedom - common causes are over-estimated experimental errors or too many degrees of freedom. If the data is over-fit, then the model is not just fitting the physical effect, but also noise and random fluctuations, and as such it loses physical meaning. $\chi^2/NDF < 1$ and $\chi^2/NDF \gg 1$ are to be avoided.

χ^2 minimization techniques are used frequently in this analysis, as they are part of the peak fitting and angular correlation fitting procedures. For peak fitting, the various parameters of the peak formula (in this case, the RADWARE peak shape) must be varied to find a combination of values for which the χ^2/NDF of the peak shape to experimental data is smallest. This will provide the most accurate fit for the data provided. Overfitting must be carefully avoided as there are many parameters in a RADWARE peak, especially when multiple peaks are superposed.

In the context of the γ - γ angular correlation performed here, a χ^2 min-

imization fit is performed to fit a curve to the graph of normalized counts against angle, such as Fig 4.1. Then, another χ^2/NDF evaluation is performed, comparing that experimental angular correlation to various theoretical correlations. Each theoretical spin assignment is evaluated 400 times for mixing ratios spanning the full possible range, and a χ^2/NDF value is found for each. Plots of this second χ^2/NDF evaluation (such as Fig. 4.2 can be used to quantify the confidence in a certain spin assignment. A 99% confidence interval is set at $\chi^2/\text{NDF} = 2$ in Ref [18]. Spin assignments that have a δ value for which $\chi^2/\text{NDF} < 2$ can be considered possible assignments.

Appendix C

Table of observed γ -rays

Table C.1: Table containing the energy (E_γ) and relative intensity (Rel. I) of each γ -ray confirmed to be real and resulting from the internal decay of ^{192}Hg through coincidence analysis. Intensities are expressed a percentage of the most intense γ -ray transition, the $2_1^+ \rightarrow 0_1^+$ transition of $E_\gamma = 422.7$ keV. γ -rays without a stated intensity were unable to be reliably fit in the singles spectrum, either due to overlapping doublet peaks or low intensities.

E_γ (keV)	Rel. I (%)	E_γ (keV)	Rel. I (%)	E_γ (keV)	Rel. I (%)
110.0(3)	— — —	793.3(1)	— — —	1285.3(1)	0.79(1)
132.9(1)	7.04(1)	796.5(1)	0.21(1)	1292.1(1)	0.25(1)
139.5(1)	0.13(2)	799.9(1)	0.10(1)	1302.3(1)	0.08(1)
173.9(1)	14.24(1)	804.2(1)	— — —	1306.7(1)	0.07(1)
201.2(1)	— — —	808.8(1)	— — —	1311.5(1)	0.07(1)
210.0(1)	0.56(1)	813.0(1)	— — —	1319.0(2)	— — —
239.2(1)	4.99(1)	824.0(1)	0.78(1)	1326.7(1)	— — —
247.1(1)	2.69(1)	839.4(1)	0.02(1)	1330.2(1)	— — —

283.6(1)	0.34(1)	844.7(1)	0.11(1)	1345.4(1)	1.04(1)
311.8(1)	1.37(1)	850.6(1)	0.03(1)	1355.0(1)	0.07(1)
323.4(1)	3.35(1)	855.1(1)	0.41(1)	1360.1(1)	— — —
334.7(1)	0.28(1)	867.4(1)	0.53(1)	1366.8(1)	1.26(1)
343.0(1)	2.76(1)	873.2(1)	0.13(1)	1376.0(1)	0.92(1)
352.3(2)	— — —	878.5(1)	0.11(1)	1380.7(1)	0.08(1)
366.1(1)	0.30(1)	886.0(1)	0.03(1)	1385.3(1)	0.00(1)
375.0(1)	1.29(1)	890.7(1)	0.02(1)	1388.9(1)	0.08(1)
378.5(1)	0.44(1)	896.8(1)	0.10(1)	1392.7(1)	0.04(1)
384.8(1)	3.07(1)	902.6(1)	0.40(1)	1398.5(1)	0.04(1)
393.3(1)	0.44(1)	907.3(1)	0.07(1)	1402.0(1)	0.05(1)
397.3(1)	1.01(1)	915.4(1)	0.35(1)	1409.2(1)	0.04(1)
403.4(1)	0.02(1)	918.9(1)	0.28(1)	1414.1(1)	— — —
411.2(1)	0.90(1)	926.7(1)	0.04(1)	1416.6(1)	— — —
422.7(1)	100.00(1)	933.0(1)	0.67(1)	1418.8(1)	0.28(1)
437.0(1)	0.25(1)	933.8(1)	0.24(1)	1422.7(1)	0.77(1)
444.7(1)	0.48(1)	940.7(1)	0.21(1)	1424.0(1)	— — —
452.4(1)	1.30(1)	944.7(1)	0.06(1)	1431.7(1)	— — —
456.5(1)	1.01(1)	950.0(1)	0.07(1)	1439.8(1)	— — —
464.5(1)	0.26(1)	955.1(2)	0.02(1)	1444.6(1)	0.16(1)
472.3(1)	0.52(1)	958.8(2)	0.04(1)	1487.2(1)	— — —
472.4(1)	— — —	962.8(1)	0.04(1)	1497.2(1)	— — —
477.3(1)	— — —	977.7(1)	0.27(1)	1517.2(1)	0.26(1)

479.1(1)	1.54(2)	980.7(1)	0.15(1)	1534.8(2)	0.08(1)
497.4(1)	— — —	985.9(1)	0.10(1)	1540.9(1)	— — —
498.5(1)	— — —	991.8(1)	0.16(1)	1571.1(1)	— — —
525.1(1)	— — —	998.0(1)	0.18(1)	1583.7(1)	— — —
534.9(1)	0.55(1)	1009.9(1)	0.13(1)	1590.6(1)	— — —
544.0(1)	1.03(1)	1013.9(1)	0.19(1)	1598.9(1)	— — —
548.9(3)	— — —	1021.1(1)	0.11(2)	1612.6(1)	0.06(1)
557.5(3)	— — —	1029.7(1)	0.35(1)	1634.1(1)	0.14(1)
559.5(1)	2.06(1)	1040.4(1)	0.17(1)	1648.8(1)	0.41(1)
562.4(1)	0.40(1)	1042.9(1)	0.26(1)	1659.4(1)	0.14(1)
565.5(1)	0.80(1)	1046.5(1)	0.04(1)	1658.1(1)	— — —
578.2(1)	0.11(1)	1052.8(1)	— — —	1660.6(1)	— — —
584.2(1)	1.89(1)	1057.6(1)	— — —	1687.1(1)	— — —
587.8(1)	0.18(1)	1063.3(1)	— — —	1711.1(1)	0.09(1)
595.2(1)	0.60(1)	1067.1(1)	— — —	1727.2(1)	0.14(1)
601.0(1)	0.02(1)	1071.0(1)	— — —	1733.5(2)	0.03(1)
608.0(1)	0.15(1)	1073.0(1)	— — —	1759.4(1)	0.15(1)
613.3(1)	0.02(1)	1080.1(1)	0.13(1)	1769.9(1)	0.06(1)
619.2(1)	1.78(1)	1087.1(1)	0.16(1)	1807.8(1)	— — —
625.4(1)	0.28(1)	1093.7(1)	0.06(1)	1812.4(1)	— — —
634.7(1)	92.02(1)	1097.2(1)	0.26(1)	1838.6(1)	— — —
643.9(1)	1.96(1)	1105.4(1)	— — —	1853.2(1)	0.05(1)
657.4(1)	0.84(1)	1112.6(1)	2.97(1)	1865.3(1)	— — —

664.7(1)	0.24(1)	1113.8(1)	0.97(1)	1894.1(1)	— — —
675.3(1)	2.42(1)	1117.7(1)	— — —	1909.9(1)	0.06(1)
676.3(1)		1122.6(1)	— — —	1927.5(1)	— — —
686.5(1)	— — —	1129.7(2)	0.08(1)	1957.1(1)	0.02(1)
690.7(1)	2.97(1)	1141.6(1)	— — —	1980.8(1)	— — —
692.6(1)	1.69(1)	1149.8(1)	— — —	2012.3(1)	0.15(1)
693.1(1)	— — —	1151.5(1)	— — —	2024.4(1)	0.07(1)
694.3(1)	— — —	1157.2(1)	— — —	2034.7(1)	0.03(1)
699.3(1)	— — —	1167.1(1)	— — —	2046.1(1)	— — —
700.6(1)	— — —	1171.4(1)	— — —	2052.4(1)	— — —
707.7(1)	— — —	1173.5(1)	— — —	2105.4(1)	— — —
711.8(1)	— — —	1177.6(1)	— — —	2115.3(1)	0.44(1)
714.0(1)	— — —	1183.8(1)	— — —	2147.6(1)	0.17(1)
716.4(1)	— — —	1186.5(1)	— — —	2206.2(1)	— — —
718.2(4)	— — —	1193.6(1)	0.42(1)	2265.2(1)	— — —
720.5(1)	— — —	1206.2(1)	0.18(1)	2289.4(1)	— — —
731.9(1)	— — —	1210.8(1)	2.02(1)	2327.2(1)	— — —
733.5(1)	1.44(1)	1226.3(1)	0.05(1)	2352.5(1)	— — —
745.4(1)	34.11(1)	1234.4(1)	0.18(1)	2388.3(1)	— — —
759.6(1)	0.67(1)	1237.2(1)	0.12(1)	2731.0(1)	— — —
762.9(1)	0.87(2)	1244.2(1)	— — —	2779.1(1)	0.04(1)
766.2(1)	0.15(3)	1251.6(1)	— — —	3002.1(1)	— — —
771.2(1)	0.05(1)	1258.8(1)	— — —	3174.5(1)	— — —

774.1(1)	1.05(1)	1266.2(1)	0.76(1)	3482.7(2)	0.01(1)
782.6(1)	0.64(1)	1267.2(1)	— — —	3961.4(1)	— — —
786.3(1)	37.67(1)	1273.6(1)	0.15(1)	4086.2(1)	— — —